

RELIGIOUS MILIEU IN MANIPUR

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Abstract

[This paper aims to reinterpret the state religion of Manipur. It involves discovering how the various beliefs of the heterogeneous populations of Manipur were assimilated into the neutralized belief system coined as Umanglaism towards the creation of a socially integrated national community and how the influences from Mahayana Buddhism and Bhakti movement led to the development of two branches of Umanglaism, viz. Sanamahism and Bhagyachandra school respectively and how these two branches enhanced the idealistic doctrines of the ruling class to serve as reactionary purposes to sustain its position of privilege. This has been done by examining the backgrounds of various Umang lais (Umang gods) and the myths associated with them. This paper attempts to show that Umanglaism survives up to the present day through syncretism, dynamic translation, absorption and synthesis.]

DEFINING UMANGLAISM

There is a considerable body of tradition and myth concerning the nature and origin of Umang Lai worship. It is also clear that a lot of intelligent people have spent a great deal of time and effort studying and concentrating only on its general nature as an abstract and idealistic hypothesis. On the other hand, a section of scholars is trying to define Umang-lai worship under the fold of Sanamahism. This delayed scholarly recognition of Umanglai worship as a religious factor which is associated with the state formation and nation-building process of Manipur. Although critics have arrived at no satisfactory interpretation of Umanglaism (coined for the purpose of this article as there is no appropriate word to denote the system of beliefs surrounding Umang lai worship), their contribution towards the development of a scientific approach to this subject should not be underestimated. The first systematic attempt to study the Umang Lai worship in detail was made by Ngariyenbam Kullachandra in his book published in 1963 called Meitei Lai Haraoba, which may be taken as the starting point for the contemporary approaches. Ngariyenbam Kulachandra was followed by Ngangbam Kumar Maibi¹, Yumshangbi Maibi², R.K Achoubisana³, and Pundit Wahengbam Lukhoi⁴.

The present work seeks to understand and evaluate Umanglai worship in dependent upon what social purpose it serves. For this study, as mentioned earlier the term *Umanglaism* is coined to denote the system of belief surrounding the worship of *Umang-lai*⁵ and the system which considers the set of beliefs held and preached by the *maibis* in the *Laiharaoba* as the doctrine. The shrine of this religious system is termed *Umang Laipham*⁶ or simply *Umang*⁷ (sacred Grove) or *Lai pung* and the deities as *Umang-lai*.

In the process of Meetei state formation which continued for centuries amidst chaos and internal conflicts, the central authority, in its attempt to create an integrated and homogeneous nation- state, syncretized numerous religious beliefs, which includes myths, rituals and local cults of the assimilated and enslaved communities, under the institutionalized single belief system which is defined as Umanglaism in this paper. According to *Loiyumba Shinyen*, the ancient written edict on social division of labour promulgated by King Loiyumba in 1110 CE, forty five lineages were assigned to look after the official pantheon of Umanglaism, which were venerated widely all over the country.⁸ This suggests that the synthesis is realized by the twelfth-century CE.

THE ORIGIN

The *Umang lai* are numerous, ranging from cosmic forces to historical figures. They include ancestors, progenitors of clans, local heroes, folk divinities, fertility goddesses, legendary personages, primitive totems, mythological figures, natural forces, *nats*⁹ and deities of other popular religions. Most of them were originally worshiped by the individual communities in their own belief systems before their cults were completely integrated into the ever expanding fold of the state religion. The pantheon of Umanglaism is formed through a process of territorial expansion of the Meetei and assimilation of immigrants from the east and west (*Nongpok* and *Nongchup baram*) into Meetei. All the folk deities encountered in the territories which were absorbed into the kingdom, and those brought by the immigrants were recognized by the Meetei state, modified to suit its own tastes and assigned to a family or clan to ensure that each deity was worshiped according to the canons of the state religion. The aboriginal backgrounds of these gods can be traced down by examining thoroughly into some of the following examples.

Nongpok Ningthou

Nongpok Ningthou, who is one of the principal gods of Umanglaism, was originally known by the title Langmai Ningthou, literally means 'lord of the Langmai people' and with various personal names viz.

Pureiromba, Keinao Chingsomba, etc. The Selloi Langmai hills, 8 km east from Kangla, were the ancestral territory of the Langmai people [Still today many Langmai families like the Nongmaithem are settled near the Selloi Langmai hills]. This place appears to have been the stronghold of Langmai Ningthou worship. The opening lines of the archaic text Nongmaijing Chingoiba (account of the Langmai Hills) clearly mentions that the mountain situated in the east and beyond the rivers [Imphal, Kongba, Iril] is the abode of Keinou Chingsomba, the Lord of the Langmais. The ancient text Tharon tells us that Selloi-Langmai hill was divided into five territories, which had their own ancestral divinities, probably apotheosized tribal chieftains which were later eulogized as the five pillars of the Selloi-Langmai country.

Territories	Divinities
Andro	Andro Khonba (?) Panam Ningthou [chief of Panam]
Keinou	Tariya, the Keinou Lakpa [chief of Keinou]
Wakha	Purieromba, the Wakha Rakpa [chief of Wakha]
Chingyai	Chingsomba, the Chingyai Rakpa [chief of Chingyai]
Chingshang	Pallung Ningthou, the Chingshang Rakpa [chief of Chingshang]

Table 1. Five territories of Selloi Langmai and their respective divinities.

In the course of time, these five divinities belonging to the five territories of Langmai hills were integrated into a single god called Langmai Ningthou and their personal names became the aliases or manifold forms of the deity. This shows that the social organization of the communities inhabiting the Langmai hills underwent a change from tribalism into chiefdom, which later on came to be known as Angom principality.

Fig 1: Assimilation of the five folk divinities into one god.

It is possible that Langmai Ningthou rose to the rank of highest divinity of Umanglaism with his new title or name *Nongpok Ningthou* after what the archaic secular text *Naothingkhong Phambal Kaba* describes as the uprooting of the Selloi-Langmai people by the Meetei king Ura Konthouba (r. 568-658 CE). After this conflict, the Selloi-Langmais seemed to be assimilated into Meetei and their deity Langmai Ningthou was given the title Nongpok Ningthou which means "Sovereign of the East." The name itself reveals that it was given by Meetei and that the deity originally belonged to the Selloi-Langmai territory, which was situated to the east of Kangla, the capital of Meetei. The deity is first mentioned in the *Cheitharon Kumpapa* during the reign of Khagemba (r. 1597-1652) in these words:

"In the year of Ningthoujam Khari 1570 kumsak ... Apanbi was symbolically married to Nongpok at Chingkhhei."¹⁰

Most of the important surviving shrines of Langmai Ningthou are located on the Langmai hills and its vicinities. For instance, (1) Nongpok at Yairipok (2) Panam Ningthou at Andro village (3) Nongpok Ningthou at Khoirom (4) Pureiromba at Lamlai (5) Nongpok Ningthou at Engourok (6) Pureiromba at Naharup (7) Nongpok Ningthou at Takhel (8) Pureiromba at Bamon Kampu (9) Nongpok Ningthou at Charangpat Maning (10) Waroi ching Malang Lamhuiba at Waroi Ching (11) Nongpok at Chandrakhong.

These shrines are institutionalized under the principles of Umanglaism. But there are also several other sacred sites of Langmai Ningthou on the Langmai hills, which till now continues to remain independent or loosely beyond the fold of Umanglaism. For examples, the sacred sites of Chingyai, Kharong, Isingchaibi, Nungpak Khul, and Chingoi. As they remained outside the institutional system of Umanglaism these shrines were absorbed by Hinduism in the post-Charairongba period. For instance, the shrine of Chingyai was recognized as the shrine of Mahadeva (a Hindu god) by King Chandrakirti (r. 1850-1886 CE) and assigned one Gossaimayum family to manage the shrine.¹¹

Another popular *Umang lai* which is worshiped around Langmai hill is the duo Puribi and Puraba. These sibling gods originally belonged to the Selloi Langmai people since most of their myths such as searching for their widow mother who left them and married to another man, trapping of magical bird *waba* [pheasant], who blessed them with wealth and prosperity, and killing of their step-father and their wicked mother are all set in the Langmai hills and its vicinity. *Waba* seems to be a primitive totem of a tribe who inhabited in the hills before the bird was begun to be identified with the Supreme god

Atiya Kuru Sidaba in the post-Khagemba literatures. There are only three institutionalized shrines of duo gods at Moirang Kampu, Kongpal and Ningthoubung. The distribution of the shrines of Puribi and Puraba up to the fertile banks of the Kongba River in the south suggests the expanding of the Selloi-Langmai settlement into this river banks. It seems that the Selloi Langmai people, who had been extending their settlements up to the banks of the Kongba River in the south, came into conflict with the Meeteis around the sixth century probably on their attempt to conquer new land for cultivation. The well-established account of the attack of Haokap Hills by the Selloi Langmais by trespassing into the territory of Meetei during the reign of Meetei king Ura Konthouba (r. 568-658 CE) suggests their expansionist policy. The clash between the Selloi Langmai people and the Meeteis under the Ningthouja dynasty with the final victory of the latter are well expressed in *Naothingkhong Phambal Kaba* and the royal chronicles. According to the *Moirang Ningthourol Lambuba*, the Meetei king Ura Konthouba (r. 568-658 CE) defeated the Langmais under their leader Kumpa Naosang Wahangcha at a place called Khuroi,¹² which is probably the present-day Khurai. These are only a few examples of how the gods of the Selloi Langmai people or Angom were integrated into the state pantheon.

Thangjing

Thangjing is one of the four cardinal Umang lais¹³. He is eulogized as Kege Thangjing Koiren Ningthou. In another ritual song Thangjing is glorified as “*Thangjing Ningthou-o, Thangjing Koiren Ningthou, Chaoba Koiren Ningthou, Sangba Koiren Ningthou...*”¹⁴ He was in the beginning a non-Meetei divinity with an influential following among the people of Moirang principality. The name of the deity reveals that the god belonged to the Koireng¹⁵ communities before he became the main deity of Moirang, which was also formed after consolidating several communities. In the past, the Koireng tribe settled on the Thangjing hill. Owing to the repeated incursion by the Moirangs they migrated from Thangjing. For instance, according to the *Moirang Ningthourol Lambuba* [the chronicle of the Moirang kings] the Moirangs under King Thingre Nachaoba raided the Koireng tribe settled on the Yoiren Khunkum hills, in which one Nungnangcheng was defeated.¹⁶

The god Thangjing came on the scene as the Umang lai [Umang god] after Moirang came under the sway of the Meetei. Since Moirang was located on the south-western direction of the Meetei territory, the deity was transformed into the state god who guarded the south-west direction. His new personality

itself reveals his aboriginal beginning. According to *Moirang Ningthouren Lambaba*, the royal chronicle of the Moirang principality, Thangjing is described as the divine Ningthou (chief) of Koiren people, the progenitor of the Kege clan, the protector of all animals both domestic and wild and the Lord of Mahui tribe. It seems that the deity originally belonged to a herding community. It is mentioned in the Chronicle that the Moirang principality was an amalgamation of different communities following their own primitive form of belief systems and that during the reign of Fang Fang Ponglunganba, all these beliefs were assimilated into a single religious system with Thangjing as the central figure. When the cult of Thangjing was absorbed into Umanglaism, the folk divinities associated with the deity began to be identified with other Umang gods. For instance, Goddesses Ayang Leima Ahal and Ayang Leima Atonbi were originally associated with fertility and agriculture as it is evidenced from the ritual songs glorifying them.¹⁷ In the course of time, they appeared as consorts of Thangjing when the cult of Thangjing became prominent in Moirang. And when Thangjing began to be identified as an Umang lai, the two goddesses also began to be identified with Panthoibi, the more adorable goddess of Umanglaism. Thus, Goddess Ayang Leima Pantoibi came into being.

Konthoujam Lairenbi

Goddess Konthoujam Lairenbi, [lit. means goddess of Haorok Konthou people] as the name suggests, was first worshipped by the Haorok Konthou community (present day Haorokjam and Konthoujam lineages), who in the course of time appeared as one of the important Umang goddesses when Haorok Konthou was absorbed into Meetei. In the genealogy of the Haorok Konthou clan, she was referred to as the progenitor of the Konthoujam clan. According to the text, *Konthoujam Nongkaron* (Heaven's ward journey of Konthoujam Goddess)¹⁸ the name of the goddess is Chingphuron Konthousu, who was the daughter of Huimu Leima. The name of her father was not recorded. In the *Loiyumba Shinyen*, the Konthoujam clan was assigned to look after the worship of Huimu Leima, not Konthousu. The stone inscription at the Konthoujam village shows that King Khagemba (r.1597-1692 CE) lifted compulsory state duty for the Konthoujam lineage for worshipping goddess Huimu Leima. This can be comparable with Soraren (the sky god) lifting up the hardship of the Haorok Konthou clan when he took Konthousu in marriage in the myth of Haorok Konthoujam Lairenbi. The above text seems to be composed in much later period referring to King Khagemba lifting the

hardship of the Haorok Konthou community. The text is probably written in the Hindu period (post-Pamheiba) since there is the reference of Soraren identifying with Indra (Hindu sky god) who rides on his two-headed white elephant and armed with lightning bolt.

ALL-ABSORBING GODS OF UMANGLAISM

From the above few examples, it is seen that the Meetei under the Ningthouja dynasty absorbed the deities of the conquered or assimilated peoples into their own pantheon. The genius of Umanglaism lay precisely in this ability to absorb the gods of the conquered territories and enslaved communities.

Now, it may be possible to identify which gods could absorb other deities. Nongpok Ningthou, Panthoibi, Pakhangba and Yumjao Leima are known for their ability to absorb local and foreign gods. They can be considered as the all-absorbing gods of Umanglaism. According to Pundit Wahengbam Lukhoi among the Umang gods, Nongpok Ningthou, Panthoibi and Pakhangba have many *langon*¹⁹ [which can be loosely translated as transmigrations or incarnations].

The following is the names of the aboriginal and foreign divinities which are absorbed into the all-absorbing gods Pakhangba, Panthoibi, Nongpok Ningthou, Yumjao Leima.

NONGPOK NINGTHOU: Pallung Ningthou, Keinou Chingsomba, Pannam Ningthou, Tariya, Pureiromba, Saram Thangkhul, Nongpok Malang Lamheiba, Awang Pakhang Yoirenba, Angouba Langmai Ningthou.

PANTHOIBI: Khabi Lengnaomombi (Legendary Amaibi), Tampha Wangamlon (Ningthouja Goddess), Tupi Nang yek Chanu (Amaibi), Ayang Leima (Moirang goddess), Durga (Hindu deity).

PAKHANGBA: Nongda Lairen(Historic king), Naothingkhong Pakhangba (historic king), Saram Thangkhul Pakhangba (Thangkhul god), Chothe Thangwai Pakhangba, Lainung Loncha Pakhangba, Loidam Thaja Pakhangba (the moon god),Nongdren Lairen Pakhangba, Thangkhul Huitop Pakhangba, Langmaidong Pakhangba, Guru Nongsaba, Govindajee (Hindu deity), Khagemba (historical king).

YUMJAO REIMA: Areinu, Taritnu, Mairenhoubu chanu Nongta nongkhal Rembi, Yaibirok (ancestress of Ningthouja clan), Shri Tara Devi (Mahayana Buddhist goddess), Soibol Yairen chanu, Langmai Liklu Louthibi Pitanga (folk divinity of the Selloi Langmai or historic figure), Maram Chanu Engallei (folk divinity of the Maram tribe), Langol Tarung Lairenbi (goddess of Kabui community), Thongak Lairenbi, Kundong Lairenbi.

It has already been discussed in brief how Nongpok Ningthou came to be identified as the god who guided the east. Of all these gods, Pakhangba has the extraordinary power to absorb not only the local divinities but also the deities of other popular religions. The gods whose name having the suffix Pakhangba ranges from cosmic gods to progenitors amounting to more than 20 in numbers. Of them Nongda Lairen Pakhangba, Thangcha Leera Pakhangba, Leinung Loncha Pakhangba, Saram Thangkhul Pakhang, Loidam Thaja Pakhangba and Laiyingthou Pakhangba²⁰ are prominent. As the name suggests Saram Thangkhul Pakhangba and his consort, Saram Thangkhul Nurabi belonged to the Thangkhul community of north east Manipur. The two Thangkhul gods were accorded a regular place in the all pervading Umanglism when Meetei political influence spread to areas inhabiting by the Thangkhuls. Saram Thangkhul Pakhang and Saram Thangkhul Nurabi began to be identified as Pakhangba and his consort Saram Nurabi as Panthoibi. In some cases, Saram Thangkhul is also identified with Nongpok Ningthou. This shows the gravitation of Pakhangba and Nongpok Ningthou to the Thangkhul god.

There is an Umang-lai venerated at Thangmeibang named Naothingkhong Pakhangba. This deity is none other than the historical King Naothingkhong (r.663-763 CE). King Khagemba is also worshipped by the name of Pakhangba at Malom, 5 km away from Imphal.²¹ Like the influential queens who were integrated into the deity Yumjao Leima, the influential kings were also integrated into the deity Pakhangba. Pakhangba also appeared as the male counterpart of various female divinities. When Meetei rose to power and extend their influence in the hills adjoining their territory, their patriarchal god Pakhangba absorbed all other local goddesses through the technique of marriage. For example, Liksanu Saphabi of Kabui Thangal Community, Khamlang Taobi of Chothe tribe, Chotenu of Kom tribe and Leiyoi Nurabi of Langmeidong were all established in the myth as the consorts of Pakhangba. This shows absorption of aboriginal goddesses of different communities into the cult of Pakhangba.

Pakhangba is symbolically and iconographical represented by a snake with the antlers of *Sangai* (Brow Antlered deer). The dragonic symbol of Pakhangba also suggests the synthesis of two totemic belief systems – snake and stag worshipping. Snake is the totem animal of the Ningthouja dynasty. Still today the extended families of the dynasty are forbidden to eat snake-like fishes and vegetables. They respect them as their ancestors. Sangai is associated with the Luwang clan. The Chakpas also considered deer as their totem animal.

It is worth mentioning here that the legendary king of the Luwangs, Pudangkoi Khutkoiba was transformed into a *Sangai* [brow antlered deer] and was accidentally hunted down by his younger brother. Knowing that it was his elder brother the Luwang king preserved its head with horns in the palace. In an inauguration of a royal boat of the Luwang king, the head of the *Sangai* was fixed on the stern of the boat. When Luwang was integrated into Meetei, this tradition continued in the making of royal boat [*Hiyang Hiren*] of the Meetei kings. The stern of the royal boat of the Meetei king was decorated with an artificial head of a *Sangai* with horns, and the side of the boat is decorated to resemble the body of snake. The design of the boat is a dragon with horns. The iconography of Pakhangba resembles the royal boat. Pakhangba also played a significant role in consolidation of different communities into a kinship. For example, one myth of Pakhangba says that he took seven wives, and from each wife the seven clans of Meetei were descended. The myth shows the consolidation of different communities into one nation and classification of them into seven clans. In the post Khagemba period, Pakhangba began to be identified as *Paphal* (mystic diagram or *yantra*; commonly various forms of coiled serpent or dragon biting its tail or ouroboros) with the coming of Tantrism.

In the different period of time, the immigrants from the east and west were assimilated by providing wives, *yumnak* (family title) and *yek* (clan). The gods and cults brought by them were also assimilated into Umanglism. This may be symbolized by a marriage between foreign and native *Umang lais*. For example a Hindu community from the west, either migrated to or was enslaved by the Meetei. They were allowed to shelter at Thinungai. They were the worshipper of Rama. The god brought with them was renamed as Laiyingthou Ramji Ningthou and provided a native wife by the name of Leibak Leima, and they were recognized as Umanglai. Similarly, Goddess Kalika of Saktism was also absorbed into Umanglism and renamed as Lalleima (Goddess of war) [*Huiren Lalleima, Kbagi Lanchei Subi, Kalika Athoibi*]²². She was married to the Umanglai Khaplangba. She is also worshiped as Umang lai at Laphupat, Hangun and Thangkham.²³ The Mahayana Buddhist goddess Shri Tara Devi²⁴ is worshipped as Yumchao Lairenbi at Yumnam Huidrom and Sammi Devi as Lai Khurembi at Uripok²⁵, etc.

From the above examples, it is seen that Umanglism recognized the existing divinities of the aboriginals and also the gods brought by the immigrants who were absorbed into Meetei society. Therefore, Umanglism was acceptable to all the communities who were politically and socially united

under the Meetei fold. This transformed the social problems created by the confrontation between different communities towards the unification. The next section will discuss about the emergence of a new branch of Umanglaim called Sanamahism, which emphasizes the rituals and philosophy of Tantric Buddhism.

THE ELEMENTS OF TANTRIC BUDDHISM IN THE MEETEI MYTHS

Atiya Guru Sidaba, Coiled Snake god Pakhangba and Sanamahi

Buddhism was universal in all the neighboring countries of Manipur. Burma, Ahom Tai, Tibet, Thailand, Combodia, Laos and China were all Buddhist countries. The Tibetans follow Lamaism, which is the synthesis of two rival religions, Bon-po, the pre-Buddhist religion of Tibet, and Buddhism. The Ahom- Tais followed Phra-Along, which is an off-shoot of Mahayana Buddhism. In these countries, Gautam Buddha was known by various names. For instances, the Thais called Buddha as Somona-Codom, the Peguers called him Samana Khutama²⁶; the Shan called him Phra; the Ahom-Tai called him Phura or Phra or Phra-Along and the Chinese called him Po or Foe or Phat²⁷ and the Cambodian, Prah.

“Buddha is variously pronounced and expressed *Boudh, Bod, Bot, Bad, Budd, Buddou, Boutta, Bota, Budso, Pot, Pout, Pota, and Pouti*. The Siamese (Thai) make the final T or D quiescent, and sound of the word is Po; whence the Chinese still further vary it to *Pbo* or *Fo*. In the Talmudic dialect the name is pronounced as Poden or Pooden; whence the city, which once contained the temple of Sumnaut or Suman-nath, is called Patten-Sumnaut. The broad sound of the U or Ou or Oo, passed in the variation Patten into A, pronounced Ah or Au; and in a similar manner, when the P is sounded B, one come across with Bad, Bat and Bhat. All these are in fact no more than a ringing of changes on the cognate letters B and P, T and D. Another of his name is *Saman*, which is varied into *Soman, Somono, Samana, Suman-nath, and Sarmuna*. From this was borrowed the sectarian appellation of Samaneans, or Sarmanean. A third is Gautama, which is indifferently expressed *Gautameh, Godama, Godam, Codam, Cadam, Cardam, and Cardama*.”²⁸

There was not a single royal court of the Southeast and Far East Asian kingdoms and empires, which was not influenced by Buddhism. Landlocked by the Buddhist nations and also located along a trade route and a route to Buddhgaya, Manipur survived from the complete sway of Buddhism through the absorption- mechanism of its state religion Umanglaim in which the foreign pantheons, cult and myths were always integrated into the host religion;

even the personalities of the foreign deities were developed very differently from their origin. This section is an attempt to define what is indigenous and what is foreign in Sanamahism, which arose as a sect of Umanglaim since the 17th century with some features of Mahayana or Tantric Buddhism.

The influence of Buddhism on the indigenous religion of Manipur remains a fascinating problem for the scholars. Recently, there has been an attempt by some scholars to open the question through archeology. This section is an attempt to re-open the problem from the view point of comparative mythology. If Buddhism had reached Manipur, some archaeological evidence of Buddhism should have been forthcoming. In the excavation of a secondary burial mound at Sekta, 18 km north-east of Imphal on the bank of river Iril, conducted by the Archaeology Survey of India in association with the Department of History, Manipur University in 1991; a bronze relic casket typical of Buddhist origin was excavated.²⁹ Another similar relic casket of silver was also excavated from Lamboiching, Chingmeirong. Besides these two artifacts, many icons of Buddhist pantheon are also recovered from the valley. They are shown in the following table.

Sl.	Particular	Place of Recovery	Custodian
1	White marble Buddha	Utlou Langpok	Manipur State Museum
2	Wooden image of Buddha	Kakching	
3	Bronze Image of Buddha	Tera Keithal, Imphal	
4	White marble Buddha seated with cross legs on a single lotus pedestal	Langthabal, Imphal	
5	White marble Buddha with broken head with some carving	Kakching	
6	Bronze Image of Buddha	Khamnam Keithal, Imphal	
7	Bronze Image of Buddha in anjali mudra	Erengbam Leikai, Imphal	Mutua Museum
8	Marble image of Buddha	-do-	
9	Marble image of Buddha	Tengnoupal, Chandel dist.	
10	Wooden image of Buddha	Bamol Leikai	
11	Bronze icon of Bodhisattava seated in kneeling posture.	Nongmaiching hill	Mutua Museum
12	Remains of stone votive stupa	YaikulJanmasthan	Mutua Museum

Table 2: Buddha icons excavated and collected from Manipur.

All of these icons of Buddha and Bodhisattva are all portable and small in number. From these findings generally one can consider the following three possible postulates:

- 1) They were brought by the Buddhist immigrants (*Nongpok Haram*) from the east who were absorbed into Meetei
- 2) They were brought by the Burmese invaders or Buddhist pilgrims on their way to Buddhagaya.
- 3) They were collected by the Meeteis as war booties in their invasions into Burma.

There is also one statue of Buddha which is still worshiped today as the Hindu god Mahadeva at Ingourok. The statue is 5'7" high. Gangmumei Kabui writes, "These sculptures reflect the prevalence of Buddhism in the kingdom of Manipur as the Shans of Kabaw valley, who became the subjects of the kingdom, were Buddhists from the middle of the fifteenth century during the reign of King Kiyamba."³⁰ The image at Kharam near Kajikhul, made by Khagemba, has the face like Burmese Buddha.³¹ L. Kunjeswori also writes, "The discovery of the votive stupa constitutes the testimony of prevalence of Buddhist faith in Manipur. The place of discovery marks a sacred place for the followers of Buddhist."³² Another archaeological evidence of the influence of Buddhism in Manipur is the footprint of various Meetei kings erected in and beyond the present-day Manipur. Same design of gongs [*Senbung*] use in pagodas is also widely used in the temples of Manipur. The white canopy used by the Meetei king symbolizes *Dharma* as used by the kings of other Southeast Asian kingdoms. There are also four places, which are literally connected with Buddhism.

- 1) Lamboi-Khongnangkhang in Imphal West district situated on the Imphal-Iroisemba road. The place name can be literally translated as 'the pepal tree of monk' which can be logically interpreted as a Buddhist monastery.³³
- 2) Lamboi-ching is situated on the Chingmeirong hill in the Imphal West district. The name literally means 'hill of monk'. It is the same place where a bronze relic casket was accidentally excavated.

The following table shows few Buddhist loan words now use as Meeteiron.

Meeteiron	Buddhist terms	meaning
Upai	Upaya-kaushdya	Skilled means
Sun[eg.sun chatpa]	Sunyata[from Sunya]	Void, emptiness, zero
Kayat[eg. Hakchang Kayat]	Kaya [as Dharma -kaya]	Body of essence

Aran-khubam	Arah	Self-enlightenment
Budhi-lousing	Bodhi (Pali- Sanskrit)	awakened
Arong	Along (Shan)	Bodhisattava
Phura	Phra (Shan)	Buddha
Phura	Paya (Burmese)	stupa
Sanga	Sangha(Pali- Sanskrit)	association/ company
Sanaching-sumeru	Sumeru or Meru	A sacred mountain in hindu and Buddhist cosmology
Vraja	Vraja	Thunder-storm(eg. Vrajayana sect)

Table 3: Buddhist loan words

Buddhism was not unknown in Manipur is also evidenced from the archaic literatures. The archaic text *Khongchomnupi Nongkaron* writes, ‘the Kabos of the eastern country worship their god named Phura Lainingthou Senpi Kabo Sendreng (Buddha).’³⁴

During the reign of Chingthangkhomba two court scholars Nanda Haoiba and Rasananda Konsaba translated a Jataka story from Shan language to Meeteiron under the title “*Arong Nandakumar Laibu Ningba*” in 1787 CE. The story tells how one Dhananjoy became *Arong* or Bodhisattva. The term *Arong* means Bodhisattva in Shan language. In this book Gautam Buddha is referred as *Katama Phura*.³⁵

IN QUEST FOR ATIYA GURU SIDABA AND PAKHANGBA

A new form of god (supreme god) began to develop by the name of “Atiya-Guru Sidaba” in the religious literatures since the reign of Khagemba (r.1597-1652 CE) as an enterprise of the ruling class to reinforce its idealistic feudal ideology legitimatizing patriarchy, patron-client hierarchy, and subjugation of the enslaved people in general.

The word *Guru* is sometime written as *Kuru* since the letter ‘g’ and ‘k’ is interchangeable in the archaic Meetei script. Generally, we interpret this god as the Almighty God or the creator or the sky god. The ancient Meetei did not use *atiya* for sky. Instead, they used *nong*. The word Atiya is misinterpreted as sky. It seems as a distorted word of the Tibetan Buddhist term ‘*Atisha*’ meaning master. The same name was given by the Tibetan to Dipankara Sriijnana, a

great Buddhist saint- philosopher of 10th- 11th century.

From the name of the god, it is identified that Atiya Guru Sidaba was a guru or teacher. There is a possibility that Atiya Guru Sidaba might also be a mythical form of Atisa Guru or Guru Atisha, a Buddhist monk and teacher who contributed to the evolution of Tibetan Buddhism in the eleventh century. He was born in Bangladesh and trained in Southeast Asia and spread Mahayana or Tantric Buddhism in Tibet.³⁶ His teaching was based on *sunyavada* or 'emptiness doctrine'. To understand further, one may examine how Atiya Guru Sidaba was defined in the literatures. Atiya Guru Sidaba is a cosmic god who took part in the creation under the direction of his father Atingkok. In the text *Leithak Leikharol* Atiya Guru Sidaba defined himself in these words:

*"Atingkok Kuru Sidabana **Apakma** semge ninglakle. Macha Atiya Sidababu koutboktuna napadi kanano hangye, macha Atiya sidabana epadi nangney haina khum a. nangna epabu kbnglabadi epa **Ariba** ney"*³⁷

Free translation:

Atingkok Guru Sidaba conceived a desire to create '*apakma*'. He summoned his son Atiya Sidaba and asked him, 'who is your father?' Atiya Sidaba answered, 'You are my father.' As you identify me, you are [epa: father] 'Ariba.' The supreme goal of the discipline associated with the worship of Atiya Guru Sidaba is pithily stated in the above few sentences.

In Meeteirol, proper nouns are always terminated with *ba* or *bi* [ba for male and bi for female]. So the termination 'ba' of *Ariba* denotes that *Ari* is masculine gender. *Ariba* might be the Ari Buddhists which were disbanded by the Pagan king Anawrahta (1044-1077) of Burma after his adoption of Theravada Buddhism in the eleventh century. Although Anawrahta expelled them from the city of Pagan, the Ari monks continued to operate in Burma until the 19th century.³⁸ Ari monks were less orthodox, exemplified by their interest in earthly enjoyments. They indulged in uncanonical activities, such as eating twice a day, consuming liquor, meat and engage in illicit relations with women. They were 'well skilled in martial arts, were known for indulgence, and corrupted the doctrine. They practice tantra cults and magic, selling spells and absolution from sins.'³⁹ Ari Buddhism is categorized as Tantric form of Buddhism. Duroisell, the renowned archaeologist, revealed through archaeological finds that Burma was influenced by Mahayanism from Assam and Manipur.⁴⁰ Coming back to the above quotation, Aribas are those who know *Atingkok*. What is Atingkok? The same book *Laitbak Leikharol* defines Atingkok as under:

“... **sun mahakṭi taibangpan mapugee phambiney. Masadi sun ne, sun mahakṭi Atingkokki phambi ne**”

The text Leisemlon⁴¹ also gives a valuable hint, “*Ahangba-Sunya mahakṭi Atingkokki Phambi ney.*” These sentences show that Atingkok himself is *sun* or *sunya*. *Sun*⁴² is the corrupt word of *Sunyata*, which is loosely defined as ‘void’ from the root word “sunya” meaning “zero”. Etymologically Atingkok means ‘emptiness’ or ‘void’.⁴³ *Sunyata* is dynamically translated as Atingkok. So, the above quotation can be interpreted as under:

“Ariba are those who are able to realize *atingkok* or *sunyata* or voidness.” This shows that the ultimate goal of the Ari monks is *atingkok* or voidness or *sunyata*. Mahayana Buddhism developed the ideas of emptiness (*sunyata*). The well-known form of Tantric Buddhism is Vrajayana Buddhism. In Vajrayana Buddhism, the ultimate reality is *Sunyata*, emptiness or non-dualism.

PAKHANGBA “the Enlightened One”

Atiya Guru Sidaba’s realizing *sunyata*, which is literally represented as ‘knowing or recognizing father’ or ‘mapa khangba’ in the literatures found in Manipur, can be interpreted as “Awakened one or Enlightened one”. Another deity created on the concept of “realizing father” or “mapa khangba” was Pakhangba. Whether the deity Pakhangba [Literally, one who knows his father] is developed in the Meetei mythology in parallel with the Buddhist concept of realizing *sunyata* or nirvana deserves further investigation and research. Buddha means “one who has awakened.” The verbal root word Budh means “to be awake; to know; to perceive; to understand; become aware” which is exactly equivalent to the Meeteirol *khangba*. According to the mythology, Pakhangba was so called because he realized his father Atiya Guru Sidaba, whose name is synonymous with *sunyata*. So, Pakhangba realizing of his father means realizing *sunyata*. This suggests that Pakhangba is the dynamic translation of Buddha. It is also doubtful whether “*Pakhangba Cheng Hongba*” [offering rice to Pakhangba] which is observed on the full moon day of the Meetei lunar month *Kalen* is corresponded to the offering of rice pudding to Buddha (the Awakening One) on Buddha Purnima, which is also observed on the full moon of the month *Kalen*. But it could not be a mere accident. It is well established in the myth that Pakhangba is also called Lainingthou Sentreng. In the archaic text, *Khongjomnubi Nongkalon* Buddha is addressed as “Lainingthou Phura Sendreng.” **The deity Pakhangba is missing from the list of forty official deities venerated by the Meetei in the 12th century as mentioned in the Loiyumba Shinyen.** This suggests that Pakhangba

appear as an Umanglai identifying with Tubi Yoi Nongda Nongda Lairen, the founder of the Ningthouja dynasty, in the post-Khagemba period as an important deity in the myths influenced by Mahayana Buddhism. Pakhangba is symbolically represented by Uroboros (serpent or dragon biting its own tail), which is a universal metaphor of infinity or eternity. Analogically uroboros as a circle also represents *Sunyata* -the symbol of enlightenment of wisdom. In Mahayana Buddhism, especially Zen Buddhism the abstract uroboros symbolized absolute enlightenment. The motif that Pakhangba was named after realizing his father Atiya Guru Sidaba or sunyata is directly relevant to his mystical symbol of coiled serpent or dragon biting its tail representing enlightenment.

It is possible that “enlightened” kings were given the title Pakhangba like the title Buddha was given to “Awakened One”. Kings like Nongta Lairen, Naothingkhong, Khagemba were adored with the title Pakhangba or “the Awakened one” or “the Enlightened one” like the greatest Burmese kings adopted the titles Alongphura or the enlightened one (*laung* embryo; *pbr* Buddha).¹ For instance, the founder of the Konboun Dynasty of Burma assumed the title Alaungpaya, meaning Embryo Buddha which is similar with the title Pakhangba in Manipur. Phralaung, which means Embryo Buddha or more correctly Bodhisattva, was also worshipped separately as a deity in Manipur which will discuss in detail later in this paper.

In the later period, Pakhangba is also symbolically represented by mystical coiled snake biting its tail, forming different yantra and mandala.⁴⁴ For instance, the *paphal* (pattern) of Pakhangba or *Yumjao paphan* is parallel with the tantric *Kalsarp yog yantra* (serpent time configuration), a horoscope based on Indian astrology. According to the Indian astrology when all the planets are located between Rahu (serpent’s head) and Ketu (serpent’s tail), it is said to have *Kalsarp yog* (*kal*, time; *sarp*, serpent). It is also believed that the worship of the mystic geometrical diagram *Kalsarp yog yantra* reduces the negative effects of the *Kalsarp yoga dasa* and brings positive energy. In an MS entitled, *Paphal Lambuba*, there are 364 mystic drawings or Paphals. Yantras are often associated with Tantrism and esoteric forms of Buddhism. In Northern Thailand, *yantra* is called *Yan Phraphuttharup* (Buddha Image Yantra).⁴⁵

¹ Colin Metcalfe Enriquez, Thacker, Spink, 1916 A Burmese Enchantment ,1916, p.59, The Burmese call the pagoda “paya” or Lord, a title which has been assumed by many kings, and is applied to priests, pagodas, and Buddha figures. It is the same word as the Siamese pra.

Figure 2: Snake pattern in Indian Temple similar with Pakhangba pattern.

Figure 3: Kalsharp Yog Yantra (Indian horoscope)

Figure 4: Pakhangba Paphal(source: Roneldrajit Singh Rajkumar)

Figure 5: Paphal describing the life-substance (18th-19th centuries) similar with Kaalsarp yog Yantra (Source: Mutua Bahadur, Illustrated Manuscripts from Manipur Social And Religious Aspects, p.156)

Figure 6: Uroboros representing Ningthouja clan which is similar with the abstract uroboros representing Enlightenment of Zen Buddhism (source: Mutua Bahadur, Illustrated Manuscripts from Manipur Social And Religious Aspects)

It has been seen that the subjugation or enslavement of Luwang by the Ningthouja led to the fusion of their totems and the development of their progenitor deity represented by a snake with the antler of sangai. In the course of time this deity began to develop with the concept of ‘realizing father’ or ‘*pa khangba*’ influenced by the Mahayana Buddhism, and the god’s dragonic symbol began to develop as Uroboros (serpent or dragon biting its own tail) representing eternity and again in the later period the deity began to appear as various forms of *yantra* [mystic diagram] influenced by Tantrism. When the idea of flexibility of the icon began to conceive, one can design the icon into different mystic forms or diagrams representing different forms of martial art code, dance steps and tantric yantras and mandalas.

Fig 7: Diagram showing the evolution of Pakhangba’s symbol from a totemic snake to a mystic diagram (Adapted from the Mss *Paphal Lambuba*). The first and second diagrams show the fusion of the three clans- Luwang represented by its totem *Sangai*, Ningthouja by its totem snake and the Khuman by the head of its chief kwapa.

To understand the personalities of Atiya Guru Sidaba, Pakhangba and Sanamahi developed since the reign of Khagemba (r. 1597-1652 CE) it is worth mentioning the myth of the contest between the two brothers Sanamahi and Pakhangba for the throne of their father Atiya Guru Sidaba. This myth is known as “Nongkhong Koiba” (Circumambulation of the Universe) in Manipur.

THE MYTH OF NONGKHONG KOIBA⁴⁶

Atiya Guru Sidaba asked his sons, Sanamahi and Pakhangba, that he would give his throne to one of them who could circumambulate the universe first. On hearing this, the eldest and stronger, Sanamahi went round the universe. Pakhangba, the younger and the weaker, was favoured by his mother,

goddess Leimaren Sidaba, who told him the wisdom that going round his father's throne seven times is similar with circumambulation of the universe. Pakhangba won the contest by going round his father's throne seven times. His father was happy knowing that his second son recognized him. So, Atiya Guru Sidaba gave the name Pakhangba literally 'one who has realized his father' to his second son. When Sanamahi returned after circumambulation of the universe he found that Pakhangba had already finished his circumambulation and took the throne of Atiya Guru Sidaba. Sanamahi became angry and attacked Pakhangba, who was protected by the seven goddesses.

INTERPRETATION

The throne or seat of Atiya Guru Sidaba is described in the text *Leithak Leikbarol* as *sun* or *sunyata* (voidness) in these words "*sun mahaketi taibangpan mapugee phambiney.*" It means the throne of Atiya Guru Sidaba is *sunyata* which is also metaphorically represented as the throne or seat of Enlightenment in the Buddhist literatures. The contest between Sanamahi and Pakhangba over the throne is the contest to achieve salvation or *sunyata* or Nirvana. The two brothers followed different paths to achieve it. The elder and stronger Sanamahi followed the nobler principle, i.e. circumambulation of the universe as told by his father and his weaker brother Pakhangba followed the easy path as told by her mother, Leimaren Sidabi (the mother goddess), i.e. going round the throne of his father (similar with circumambulation of Stupa, which represents the holy mind of all Buddhas). This motif is an explanation of the different paths followed by the two rival Buddhist sects, Theravada and Mahayana, towards enlightenment. This motif also shows the common belief that circumambulation will achieve nirvana or sunyata or enlightenment. The text *Buddhavamsa* writes, "There he will circumambulate his enlightenment throne, and (then) seated at the foot of the Assattha tree that unsurpassed One, of great renown, will attain enlightenment."⁴⁷

Buddhism is divided into two major branches. They are Theravada, the way of the elders and Mahayana, the Great Vehicle. The contest between Sanamahi and Pakhangba to achieve the throne of Atiya Guru Sidaba, which is a metaphorical representation of sunyata or nirvana as stated above, suggests the rivalry between Theravada and Mahayana in their journey or path to attain salvation or the 'throne of enlightenment'. Theravada [Thera=elder; vada=doctrine] was the oldest form of Buddhism the tenets of which are based on the enlightenment of individual, self-discipline, monkhood and

following the basic ethical principles of the Buddha's teaching. The teaching of the early form of Buddhism (Theravada) shows that salvation could be achieved by few specialized persons which are represented by the motif of 'elder and stronger' in the above myth. ['Elder' for early Buddhism, and 'Stronger' for few specialists; not for common masses]. On the other hand, the philosophical tenet of 'younger' Buddhism, Mahayana, which arose in the 1st century CE, is based on the teaching that 'arah' or 'aran khubam' (in Meeteiron) could be achieved not only by few specialized stronger persons but also by common 'weaker' masses for themselves in their own mind – veneration of bodhisattvas, philosophical discussion, martial arts and with the enlistment of female deities. Theravada views that Buddha was a historical teacher of the truth whereas Mahayana sees Buddha as an earthly manifestation of a celestial Buddha. For these reasons, Theravada Buddhism views Mahayana Buddhism as a corrupt form of Buddha's teaching and also sees it as too easy. This fact is represented by the motif that the weaker and younger Pakhangba achieved the throne by adopting the easy path enlisted by his mother and other goddesses in the myth. This shows the involvement of Mother Goddess and other *lainura* (goddesses) in the contest. There were no goddesses in the early form of Buddhism (Theravada). The feminine principle makes its first appearance in Buddhism as the goddess who personified the "Perfection of Wisdom" in Mahayana Buddhism. Buddhist goddess is first mentioned in the book Prajnaparamita Sutra (translated into Chinese from the original Sanskrit c. 2nd century CE).⁴⁸ "In early Mahayana, the Prajnaparamita-sutra was perceived as a fundamental text, a tool to reach enlightenment. The text came to be worshiped in a similar way to the stupa containing the relics of the Buddha and was finally personified as a goddess, a sort of supreme female bodhisattva guiding mankind to enlightenment and sometimes described as the 'mother of all bodhisattvas'. The worship of this goddess was hoped to bring wisdom and knowledge."⁴⁹ The Prajnaparamita (goddess of perfect wisdom) tradition is represented by the motif of Leimaren Sidaba, the mother goddess, giving wisdom and guiding Pakhangba to achieve the throne of Atiya Guru Sidaba (i.e. *sunyata* or enlightenment).

Finally, it can be inferred that Sanamahi's path to attain the throne of his father represents the conservative philosophical tenets of early Buddhism (Theravada) to attain nirvana whereas the easy practice of Pakhangba enlisting his mother's wisdom represents the rebellion path adopted by Mahayanists guided by goddesses.

KING KYAMBA (r.1469-1508 CE) AND PHURA-LAI

The first diplomatic relationship between Manipur and a Buddhist kingdom ever recorded in the chronicles is the treaty concluded between King Kyamba of Manipur and King Khekhomba of Pong (Shan) in 1470 CE, after they had jointly conquered Kabo. There is a popular Hindu myth created on this event that King Khekhomba of Pong presented an icon of god *Phura* to Kyamba, who identify the deity as the Hindu god Vishnu and assigned a family to worship the deity at Lamlangtong (Lamangdong) and that the descendents of that family began to be known as *Phura lai latpam* literary means 'the family who worshiped the god *Phura*'. This myth was created by the court scholars in the 18th century to identify the god *Phura* with the Hindu god Vishnu to support their argument that Manipur followed Vaishnavism since the reign of Kyamba. R. K. Jhalajit, supporting the 18th century School, writes in his book 'A Short History of Manipur' that 'the Shan word *Phura* denoting the image of Vishnu came to the language along with the image of Vishnu.'⁵⁰

But it is a universally known fact that Buddha is called *Phura* by the Shan Buddhists. Their argument might have been based on the general belief of the Hindus that Buddha was an incarnation or *Avatara* of Vishnu. The ancient Meeteis were well aware of the fact that *Phura* and Vishnu are different gods belonging to different religions. For example, in the archaic text *Khongchomnupi Nongkaron* it is said that the Kabos of the eastern country had worshiped their god named Lainingthou Sendreng *Phura* (Buddha), and the Thongnang Mayang (Cachar) of the west worshiped their god *Pishnu* (Vishnu). In the eighteenth-century Manipuri version of the Jataka story, Gautama Buddha is referred as *Katma Phura*. Although Buddha was not an alien god to the ancient Meeteis no contemporary record gives any detail about the influence of Buddhism into the indigenous religion until the 17th century.

KING KHAGEMBA (r. 1597-1652 CE) AND PHURA

The word *Phura* first appeared in the Court Chronicle *Cheitharon Kumpapa* during the reign of Meidingu Khagemba. Here are selected records from the Cheitharol Kumbaba associated with religious activities during the reign of Khagemba.

'The year of Haokhom Mikra, Sakabda 1519 (1597 CE) Meetingu Khagemba ascended the throne when he was twenty- four years old.... The year of Loitongbam Mayang, Sakabda 1524 (1602 CE), they were victorious over Kyang, Chosengkham, Thamung and Chawai and other, totaling 177 people, were captured in battle. They also captured sculptors from Kyang....

The year of Keisam Mayang 1527 (1605 CE)... All the graves from the midst of the housing areas were made to be moved outside the (city) wall....The year of Haobam Maramba Kum Sak 1537 (1615 CE) Yipungo (prince) **Taipomba was born**....The year of Sanong 1538 (1616 CE) Meedingu Khakempa ordered to produce Meetei books and reading and writing began to be taught on a wider scale. A royal palace (Sana sangkai) with a five-tiered roof was built.... The year of Chanambam Kharoi Kum Sak 1539 (1617 CE) **Phura Laiyim** built at Wangkon [Wangoi?].... The year of Khumukcham Langmei 1543 Kum Sak (1624 CE)....

A sangkai (building) with a nine-tiered roof was built.... The year of Chongtham Tenpa 1549 Kum Sak (1627 CE) A **Phura Laiyim** was built...The year of Thiyam Khomba 1551 Utra Sankai was built. The Phura Laiyim was consecrated... The year of Nongpokpam Pangangi Kum Sak 1662 (1630 CE) Kangla caught fire. The fire reached **Phura** The year of Heirangkongjam Thawaige 1555 Kum Sak (1633 CE)...In the month of Kalen, they dedicated Kangla of Laiyengthou Nongsapa... 100 prisoners were sacrificed...In the years of Moirang Tona 1557 Kum Sak (1635 CE)... they hunted a wild ox in Thoupan and it was caught in Namum hill. It was brought to lai Kasa and the meat was distributed to each of the shrines in other villages.... The year of Chanambam Chinglou 1559 Kum Sak (1637 CE)... The kangla [shrine] of Laiyengthou Kasa was consecrated... the year of Yenkhoibam Muwa 1569 Kum Sak (1647 CE)... they were victorious over Mungyong and Kyang. They captured the royal sculptor from Kyang.”⁵¹

In the year 1617 CE, the chronicle records the construction of a temple at Wangkon in this word: “Wangkon-da *Phura* Laiyum Saiye”⁵² This passage is generally translated as “a temple on the model of Burmese *paya* or pagoda constructed at a place called Wangkon” since the word *Phura* is commonly applied to any brick temple and brick mausoleum in Manipur. Two years later it records the inauguration of the *Phura*. Three years later, in 1630 CE, it records the fire in the palace which reached the *Phura*.

Although the chronicle did not record the name of the particular god to whom the *Phura* (temple on the model of Burmese *paya* or pagoda) was dedicated at Wangkon [Wangoi?] in 1617 CE the *Cheitharol Kumbaba* recorded the construction of another *Phura* in 1627 CE. The collection of sculptors from Burma, the construction of five and nine tiered buildings [the tiers of the Buddhist pagodas are usually odd numbered] and *phura* shows the influence of Buddhism and the willingness of Khagemba to accept Buddhist elements. Since the name of the particular god to whom the phuras were dedicated was

not mentioned these phura or payas can also be interpreted as the pagoda itself. *Paya* is a religious building where Buddhist relics and ashes were venerated. In Manipur tomb or the brick structure where the relics were venerated was also known as Phura. For instances, the tomb of Gambhir Singh at Langthabal and the tomb of Badra Singh at Cheirap court are known as phura.

According to the tradition, Khagemba constructed a temple at Wangoi dedicated to his late son Taibangkhaiba who was elevated in the myths as an incarnation of the celestial Sanamahi. It is doubtful whether Prince Taipong whose birth was recorded in the Cheitharol Kumbaba in 1615 CE was Taibang Khaiba, and the phura constructed at Wangkon [Wangoi?] in 1617 as recorded in the Chronicle is the present shrine of Sanamahi at Wangoi, or it is the same temple dedicated to his dead son Taibangkhaiba. Now the problem is who is this new god Sanamahi? Among the list of official Umang Lais recorded in the edict of King Loiyumba, Sanamahi is not mentioned. But Sanamahi is worshipped as an Umang lai at Sugnu, Ahanthem and Wangoi⁵³. It shows that Sanamahi appeared as a Meetei god in much later period in the post-Loiyumba period.

SANAMAHI

The term Sanamahi is hardly recorded in the royal chronicle. Instead, Laiwahaiba was widely used. Now the name is no longer used. He is also referred to as Awang Phallou Laima Khomba (Awang Phatlou Leimakhomba⁵⁴) and Lai Taibang Khaiba. The following chronology shows the different names of Sanamahi recorded in the Cheitharol Kumbaba:

Name	Since	Period
Taibang Khaiba ⁵⁵	1685 CE up to present day	Paikhomba (r.1666-1697 CE)
Lai-wa-haiba ⁵⁶	1700 CE up to 1746	Charairomba (r.1697-1709 CE)
Phallou Khomba ⁵⁷	1733 CE up to present day	Pamheiba (r.1709-1748 CE)
Sanamahi ⁵⁸	1746 CE up to present day	-do-

The *Sanamahi Laikan* refers the deity by varieties of names, such as Awang Ningthou Yoirenba, Kanglei Ashiba, Chingu Mangal Araba⁵⁹, Meetingu Cha Yoirenba. Of all these names Sanamahi is now commonly used.

Sanamahi as *Laiwahaiba* –the god who delivered the word of God.

Literally, Lai Wa Haiba can be interpreted as the god who speaks. In

Manipuri *Mantra* is called *laiwa*. So, the deity Laiwahaiba [Laiwa= Mantra; haiba= to chant] can also be defined as the god who chants mantra. The term *wahaiba* is used to define the monk who taught or delivered the religious doctrines is evidenced from the following record from Cheitharol Kumbaba:

“In the year of Moirang Kongyampa, Sakabda 1626 (1704 CE)... The month of Sachiphu ... 20 Thursday... a *gosai muni wa haipa* and others, totaling twenty-two people, arrived.”

Here *Gossai Muni* means a ‘Bengali monk’ and *wa haiba* means ‘who delivers the words of god’. There was also a tradition of reading out religious doctrines by a learned man who is called ‘lairik haiba’. [lairik=scriptures; haiba= to speak]

According to the terminology of the deity Laiwahaiba, who would be later popularly known as Sanamahi in post- Charairomba period, is a deity who delivered the words of god.

Now the question is what are the religious doctrines delivered by Sanamahi? In the hymn of Sanamahi contained in the book ‘Khunung Lichat Sajat’ the god Sanamahi is glorified as ‘Khoimom Laiyingthou Taibang Namu Sangsang Londinnaba” which can be literally translated as ‘the god who speaks face-to- face with the mortals.’ This may be the reason why Sanamahi is commonly recorded in the Cheitharol Kumbaba by the name of Lai-Wa-Haiba [lit. Lai= god; Wa= word or discourse; haiba (verb) = to tell or to speak]. Saroj Arambam Nalini Parratt interprets the name Laiwahaiba as the “oracle god” who delivers premonition to the maibis or shamans. Arambam ongbi Memchoubi, on the other hand, says that the god who delivers prophesies to the maibis does not have particular name and that the god who speaks directly to the people is none other than Gautama Buddha.⁶⁰ **Buddha referred himself as Tathâgata, which means the one who speaks Dharma.**⁶¹ It is one of the titles of Gautam Buddha. A tathagata is a manifestation of Dhamma who can speak it, who can teach it.⁶² The tathagata is he who speaks that which is true, he who speaks that which is fundamental, he who speaks that which is ultimate. He does not speak that which is deceitful, nor does he speak that which is alien.⁶³ So, tathagatha, the other name of Buddha, is likely to be translated dynamically into Meeteirol as ‘Laiwahaiba.’

Sanamahi as Awang Phallou Khomba

Awang Phallou Khomba, or sometimes Awang Phatlou Laima Khomba, is another commonly used name of Sanamahi. The prefix *Awang* means heaven or sky. It also means north. Interestingly, Phallou or Phatlou as the name of Sanamahi is comparable with Pralaun [Phra-alaong], or aspirant to

divine honours, which epithet is given by the Burmese to all their kings, as an augury of their apotheosis, as in the case of Godama [Gautama].⁶⁴ So, Phal-lou or Phat-lou may be a corrupt word of “Phra Along” meaning Bodhisattva. As mentioned above ‘*Along*’ means ‘Bodhisattva’ in Shan language. Here it is worth mentioning that there was also a Mahayana sect called Phralong in Assam. “The Phralong sect is a section of Mahayana Buddhism, prevailing in the society of the Tai-Ahoms in north-east India, since the establishment of their country Mong-Dun-Hsun-Kam.”⁶⁵

Sanamahi as “Sacred-Semen”

According to Loina Sillon, Sanamahi is a royal title given to a special son of the Meetei king born to his queen whose mother is the Khurai Leima (Queen of Angom) as well as the Tamphasana (crown princess or eldest daughter of a Meetei king). One of the oldest books on Sanamahi is the *Sanamahi Laikan*. It was probably composed in the post-Pamheiba period.⁶⁶ In this book, the word sanamahi is first used to mean ‘liquid-gold’.⁶⁷ Literally and generally, Sanamahi means ‘Golden Semen’. The name might be the translation of the term Boddhicitta. In both Vajrayana and Sahayana Buddhism, the word “Boddhicitta” and “Sacred-Semen” is synonymous. Boddhicitra means thought of awakening or aspiration for enlightenment.

The Sanamahi Laiken gives a reference to the sexual union of Khagemba and his queen Nungthi Chaibi which union resulted to the conception of an incarnation of the celestial Sanamahi. This reference is comparable with the Tantric Buddhist practice of the union of Bliss and Emptiness, which can be achieved either by meditation or with sexual intercourse between partners. The seat of ‘Great Bliss’ is called “Nirban Phambiren Athoiba” in the text Arong Nandakumar Laibu. In his book *The Red Thread: Buddhist Approaches to Sexuality* Bernard Faure writes, “The pairing of wisdom (prajñā) and skillfulness in means (upāya), or wisdom and compassion (karuṇa) – as representing the female and male principles- is also expressed on the mythological plane by the representation of the Buddha with a feminine companion (cākti), symbolizing his energy. This perfect union, prajñôpâya, can be concretized by the union of a male practitioner with a female partner (the Tibetan yab-yum). The Great Bliss (mahāsukha) that ensues coincides with the realization of Emptiness (called vajra, diamond or thunderbolt).”⁶⁸ The motif of the sexual union between Khagemba and his wife which resulted with the mythical birth of Sanamahi as a cloud on the full moon day of the Meetei lunar month *Kalen* (the Buddha purnima day) as mentioned in the text

Sanamahi Laikan might be a metaphorical representation of Khagemba achieving the great Bliss (sanamahi) through the ritualistic sexual union. On the other hand “Sexual yogas often involve retention of semen by male practitioners. In such contexts, the semen is referred to as ‘mind of awakening’ (bodhicitta), and the movement of subtle energies through the central channel is equated with generation of the aspiration to become a Buddha.”⁶⁹ All these suggest that the Mahayanists consider semen as a synonym of consciousness. Semen is also considered as the embodiment of all the Buddhas.⁷⁰

The name Sanamahi might have been developed from this concept. The road to the Temple of Sanamahi at Wangoi was called Mayai Lambi meaning “Middle Path”. It is also possible that it was constructed with the Buddhist idea that following “the Middle Path” a soul could archive Nirvana or Buddha that is symbolized by the temple or Phura of Sanamahi itself.

MYTHS OF SANAMAHI

There are two important myths of Sanamahi. It is proposed not to present the whole story of Sanamahi in detail, as it is too vast a subject. For the present study, only the two form of Sanamahi are produced:

- 1) Celestial Sanamahi
- 2) Mortal Sanamahi

First, Sanamahi appears as the cosmic god, the eldest of the two sons [in other myths three] of the Atiya Guru Sidaba. In this version of cosmology, Sanamahi took a major role in the creation of earth. Second, he was incarnated as a son of King Khagemba.

CELESTIAL SANAMAHI

The most popular myth of Celestial Sanamahi is the contest for the throne with his younger brother Pakhangba, which is mentioned in the above section as the contest between the rivals Theravada and Mahayana schools. The text Leithak Leikharol and other texts write that the almighty god produced three sons from himself. The first son was named as *Ha*, the second son, *Ra* and the third, *Sa*. They represent air, water and fire respectively. *Ha* is Atiya-Kuru Sidaba or Guru Sidaba, *Ra* is Sanamahi, and *Sa* is Pakhangba. It can be comparable with the Bija mantra, viz Sahasrara, ha=Surya, ra=Agni and sa=Soma.⁷¹ Ch. Manihar, commenting on the creation myth contained in *Sanamahi Laikan*, an eighteenth-century text which described the development of Sanamahism since the reign of Khagemba(r. 1597-1652 CE), writes, “The symbolic use of *ha*, *ra*, *sa* to denote the three sons [Atiya, Sanamahi and

Pakhangba] of the Almighty at the outset is an instance that smacks of the influence of Tantrism.”⁷² The same book *Sanamahi Laikan* reveals that Sanamahi is associated with Tantric god Mahadeva, who is also known as Bootnat.⁷³ In the hymn called “Sanamahi Yiratpage Tengtha Laison” Sanamahi is eulogized as “Ra”.⁷⁴ Most of the religious texts on the worship of Sanamahi are associated with Tantric practices. For example, the text *Sanamahi Naiyom* prescribes mantras for the cure of physical and mental sicknesses. The texts *Sanamahi Phankhong*, *Sanamahi Mingkebeiron* and *Santhong Laigee Thouni Lairik*⁷⁵ also contain Tantric mantras. For example, “to stop the rain chant – *Hung Krung hung-krung ta ta ta ta ta ta ta ab ab. Chat buk buk hing hing buk su sa hing hing lik sal lit hing ma pan.* “to persuade a woman chant this mantra in a betel – *sang tarengnu ningkehiba-o ming tarengnu atonbi –o* “to increase the production of paddy chant- *kbuk-kbuk chi kbuk chirai nampba phachin punglen.* “to give life to a dry wood chant – *chung ching agong ying hung hing ta nyeng akta hing hing kharik kaikhoi tang ang hang buk abung pu ong buk ngangtarang.*”⁷⁶

R.S Sharma writes, “The tantras served an important social purpose by prescribing numerous rituals and remedies not only for the day-to-day diseases but also for snake-bites, mouse-bites, bites by poisonous insects, and injuries supposed to be caused by ghosts..... Rites and occult practices were supposed to avert the adverse effects of poison, planets and diseases, and drugs were to be administered accompanied by incantations..... Tantricism laid down numerous magical rituals to achieve liberation (mukti) and enjoyment (bhukti), and in fact to fulfill all kinds of the material desires (kamyani) of the people.”⁷⁷

Sanamahi as a god who sits under the tree of life:

Sanamahi is also glorified as the god who attains the *yaimaru*.⁷⁸ The Jataka story entitled *Arong Nandakumar Laibu Ningba* gives the meaning of the Meeteiron term *yaimaru* is used as a synonym of Nirvana or in Meeteirol *Nirban*.⁷⁹ Sanamahi is also eulogized as “*Pamel Upunsi da Kaidongba*” [pamel-u= tree; Punsi= Life; da= on/in; Kai= a seat ; tongba= sitting, as in the word *Phambal Tongba*(sitting on throne)]. The phrase can be translated as the god who sits under the Tree of Life. Upunsi or the Tree of Life is comparable with the Bodhi tree.

In *Sanamahi Laikan*, Sanamahi is identified as an avatar of Vishnu.⁸⁰ The text *Sanamahi Mingkebei* also supported it. It is universally known that Buddha is regarded as an Avatar of Vishnu by the Hindus. In one myth Sanamahi came in the dream of Bhagyachandra and identified himself that he was born as Asiba in Hayi Chak; in the Haya Chak he was born as Rama; in Khunung

Chak, as Krishna and in the Langba Chak, as Sanamahi.⁸¹ This shows the Hindu concept of ten incarnation of Vishnu. In the *kali yug* Vishnu was incarnated as Buddha. The myth identifies Sanamahi with Buddha. Here it will be right to mention an event from the *Cheitharol Kumbaba*:

“In the year of Kumbikhun Nathaba 1773 sakabda (1851 CE)... Thursday, the full moon day of *Fairen* as the idol of Vishnu which was kept in the early time in the temple of Sanamahi being lost a new idol of Maha Vishnu was cast.”⁸²

This shows that the image of Vishnu was worshipped along with the idol of Sanamahi in the Temple of Sanamahi long time before the period of Chandrakirti. This historical fact is also corroborated with the recognition of Sanamahi as the avatar of Vishnu by Santa Das Gossai as mentioned in the text *Sanamahi Laikan*. Why Sanamahi is identified as Vishnu is a question to be asked? The concept of Buddha as an incarnation of Vishnu is established in the myth.

Lotus Footprint in the temple of Sanamahi

There is another instance from the *Cheithron Kumbaba* that “on 31st May 1806 CE, King Chourjit visited Leishangkhong (Wangoi) to pray to Sanamahi. He cast gold on the footprint made by Khagemba.”⁸³ This shows that when King Khagemba first started the worship of Sanamahi at Wangoi, he made a footprint. Most of the footprint engravings found in the hills, for example the footprint made by Gambhir Singh at Kohima, are related to the conquest of the kings. They are the symbol of dominations and subjugations of the villages and principalities.⁸⁴ But the footprint made by Khagemba in the temple of Sanamahi at Wangoi as mentioned in the chronicle is religious rather than political. This might be made in imitation of the Buddha’s lotus footprint. Kunjeswori writes, “During the early spread of Buddhism, the foot print of Buddha was often represented in places, where he visited. This depiction of prints include [sic] the symbol of toes, lotus and swastika. The footprints, which is mostly engraved by the tribals [sic] as well as the Meitei might have been imitated from Buddhist sect.”⁸⁵

One of the interesting references of the origin of Sanamahi is given in *Sanamahi Laikan* as “Santhong Moribaramgee Lamthourakpa Khamnung yaithong singsuba”⁸⁶ which can be interpreted as the god who came from the Moribalam [country of Maurya?] of the south-western direction and spread up to every household of Khamnung. It perhaps recalls the historical fact that during the reign of Asoka of Maurya that Buddhism was propagated beyond Magadha to Burma, China and Middle East countries.

MORTAL SANAMAHI

One of the common myths of Sanamahi is his incarnation as the eldest son of King Khagemba (r. 1597-1652 CE). Here the concept of incarnation is introduced in the mythology of Manipur. "The theory of incarnation," D.N. Jha writes, "is first mentioned in the Gita and developed under the influence of the Buddhist doctrine of Bodhisattva."⁸⁷ According to the *Sanamahi Laikan*, Sanamahi was mysteriously born to Queen Angom chanu Nungthil Chaibi, consort of King Khagemba, as a cloud on the full moon day of the Meetei lunar month *Kalen*⁸⁸ which is corresponding to the *Buddha Purnima*, the birthday of Buddha.

Historicity of Sanamahi

The historicity of the eldest son of Khagemba who became the Lai is problematic. The secular text Sangai Phamang and other genealogical books recorded about his parentage as below:-

"King Mungyamba begets King Khagemba by Queen Keinao Chaopombi. King Khagemba had three consorts, Queen Taipombi, Queen Angom Chanu Nungthil Chaibi and Queen Kongpam Chanu. He had five sons, (1) Prince Khongchomba, also known as Leishang Hiden Taba, (2) Prince Khunjaoba [Later King] and (3) Prince Tonana born to Queen Taipombi. (4) Prince **Taibang Khaiba was born to Queen Angom Chanu Nungthil Chaibi. He became *Lai* (god).** (5) Prince Kyamba was born to Queen Kongpam Chanu. Prince Kyamba died without leaving any male issue. Prince Khunjaoba followed his father to the throne, but he died without any male issue. The eldest son Khongchomba was also issueless."

The divinity Sanamahi was first recorded in *Cheitharol Kumbaba* by the name of Taipang Khaipa. According to the Chronicle entitled *Khannung Yingal Leisana*, Taipang Khaipa was born in the year of Haobam Marampa (1537 Sakabda/ 1615 CE)⁸⁹. It is corroborated with the court chronicle *Cheitharol Kumbaba* which records the birth of a son of King Khagemba named Taipomba in the same year 1615 CE.⁹⁰ It is possible that Prince Taipomba was named after the victory of the kingdom of Tai Pong in the preceding year 1514 CE as the name Taipomba is the short form of *Taipong Ngamba* meaning "Victor of Tai Pong". For example, the names of Meetei kings Mayamba (Maya[ng Nga]mba) is a combination of two words Mayang and Ngamba [meaning Victor]; Kabomba for Kabo Ngamba meaning 'Victor of Kabo'; Kyamba for Kyang Ngamba meaning 'Victor of Kyang'; Khakemba for Khaki Ngamba

meaning 'Victor of Khaki' and Mungyamba for Mungyang Ngamba meaning 'Victor of Mungyang.' It is a royal custom that a prince or a princess was named after the eventful occasion that fall on their birth. Khakemba or Khagemba was so named because he was born in the same year when his father Mungyamba was victorious over the Khakis; Gambhir Sing was named Samuphaba [Captor of elephant] as he was born during the elephant hunting expedition conducted by his father King Bhagyachandra at Koubru; Prince Keifa Sana [lit. Captor of Tiger] was so named because he was born during the tiger hunting expedition conducted by his father King Nara Singh. It is possible that Price Taipomba, whose year of birth is recorded in the *Cheitharol Kumbaba* as 1615 CE, is none other than the divinity Taipang Khaiba, who was developed in the later myth as an incarnation of Celestial Sanamahi.

The prince who had become Lai (god)

Prior to Prince Taibangkhaiba, there are also two princes who are recorded in the chronicle and the royal genealogy as "*lai oikhiye*" meaning "the one who had become lai [god]." They are Prince Yishing Chaiba, son of King Kabomba (r. 1524-1542 CE), and Prince Lanhang Chaiba, who is recorded in the Cheitharon Kumbaba as 'Lai oiye' in 1578 CE.⁹¹ Prince Yishing Chaiba⁹² is worshiped as an Umanglai and as an incarnation of Sanamahi at Nagamapal in Imphal. Here the problem is what does 'lai oiye' mean? In the Cheithrol Kumbaba it is stated that the first seven kings of the Ningthouja dynasty are lais. "*makhoi lai oi mioipa taretma aside mangkhiba sikhiba mafam kbangday.*"⁹³

The translation of the text runs does: "These (kings) were like divinities, and no one knew much about these seven persons even as to how they disappeared or where they died."⁹⁴

The editors of the Cheitharol Kumbaba, Khelchandra and Iboongohal, interpret it as adopting the life of a monk by the great kings of India comparing with the *samyasi* or ascetic *sanskara* of the Hindu society. It is impossible to give the most convincing interpretation of the sentence since it cannot be treated as a primary source. It is commonly found in almost all the chronicles of the dynasties of kings claiming their descent from gods or great personalities. The motif of the seven kings of Lai is also comparable with the Burmese annals Maharazven in which the first seven Burmese kings were recorded as the Nats.⁹⁵

Therefore, it may be presumed that Prince Taibang Khaiba, who is recorded *lai oikheye* in the royal genealogy, because he was not seen again, whether he was lost or death is unknown. On the other hand, Prince Lanhang Chaiba

was recorded in the Cheitharon Kumbaba as “lai oiye”⁹⁶ in the year 1578 CE which is a present tense meaning “he becomes lai” in 1578 CE. This shows that his becoming of lai does not mean he was not seen again or mysteriously lost, but his becoming of lai is known to the people. In the eighteen century, the saint princess Bimbabati, daughter of King Chingthangkhomba, was also called “Sicha Laioibi” - the princess who had become lai. She became a Vaisnava saint. Her death account was also unknown. She was worshipped as a consort of Govindajee in the royal palace of Manipur and also at Nabadwip Purana Raj Bari, West Bengal. In the nineteenth-century Rajkumar Norendrajit Singh, popularly known as Sana Chahi Ahum, son of King Chourjit (r.1804-1814 CE) was captured for revolting against his cousin King Chandrakirti and sent to Andaman Island. Later, he fled from there and became a Tantric monk. His death account was also unknown. Today he is venerated as a lai in Tripura and Cachar. From the instances of the second two royalties, Sicha Laioibi and Sana Chahi Ahum, it can be inferred that they were called lai because they renounced the material life by adopting the life of a monk. The other influential royalties who had adopted the life of a monk and worshiped as *lai* in temples are the Saint-King Chingthangkhomba, whose idols are worshipped at Yaikul Janmasthan and Nabadwip; King Garibniwaz, at the temple of Ramji Prabhu and Prince Ananta Sai, at the temple of Shri Bijoy Govindajee. These royalties adopted the life of monks. It is corroborated with the Buddhist Manipuri text *Arong Nandakumar Laibu Ningba* that an attempt to renounce the material life to attain Nirvana by adopting the life of a monk is referred as “*Phura Khoiyum Lai oikhegay taoba...*”⁹⁷ It is possible that Prince Taibang Khaiba may have also adopted the life of a monk to attain salvation; that may be the reason why he was given the title of Sanamahi or the golden semen, or Enlighten-Semen, which is a synonym of Bodhicitra. There is also one possibility that the immature death of Prince Taipong led him to be elevated to the position of Lai as in the case of Burmese *nats*.

Sanamahi is also referred as Sanamahi Apoiba. Pundit N. Khelchandra translates the word *apoiba* as ‘Stray’ or “wandering away from home.” In *Meeteirol* (Manipuri), monk is called *lampoiba*.⁹⁸ The name implies that Sanamahi as a monk - “*Sanamahi lamboiba*”. The incarnation of Sanamahi as the eldest son of Khagemba who became the *lai* was probably developed under the influence of the Buddhist doctrine of Bodhisattvas.

Mortal Sanamahi Renouncing the Palace life

The Ningthourol⁹⁹ states that Sanamahi, unlike other mortal children,

grew up quickly. This motif is comparable with the birth of Arong Nandakumar, a Bodhisattva as mention in the Buddhist literature Arong Nandakumar laibu Ningba “*Koijum laigee machanina yangna achao lepphare.*”¹⁰⁰ This line can be translated as “Bodhisattva Nandakumar, being a son of God, grew up quickly.” This motif is comparable with the birth myth of Gautama Buddha.

Another important motif of the Sanamahi is that the mortal Sanamahi mysteriously left the palace-life and became a *lai* by hanging his royal regalia on a tree at Apong Yingkhoh. This episode is written in the *Sanamahi Laikan* as follows:

“*Charei Phiroi Punamabu, Punung Maphurit naachingna pamen usa thakta yallammaga, chingu madom lai oikhiye haidabara.*”¹⁰¹

This motif is comparable with the Sakya princes renouncing the material world by hanging their clothes and jewellery on a tree and adopting the life of monk as mentioned in the Buddhist story about Upali.

Sanamahi reflected on the mirror

In another myth, Sanamahi was reflected on a mirror as King Khagemba wished to see him again after he was mysteriously left the palace.¹⁰² This ritual is comparable with the mirror ritual of the Tantric Buddhism. As Alex Wanyemen writes, “the early Buddhist use of the mirror as a metaphor of the mind,... and then in Buddhist tantric ritual to the washing of the mirror which a deity was reflected therein.”¹⁰³ Still today the mirror ritual is practiced by the *maiba* in Manipur to see the image of Sanamahi.

The authors of the Buddhist elements

Although the myths of Sanamahi are associated with Mahayana Buddhism, there is no real proof that Sanamahi is Buddha. Besides, Sanamahi is not worshiped under the fold of Buddhism. As have been seen, not all the gods of Mahayana Buddhism were known in Manipur and even Buddha was a mere adjunct in the mythology. However, the above considerations reveal that the celestial Sanamahi is the mirror image of Buddha and mortal Sanamahi of Bodhisattva. When they were absorbed into Umanglism they were treated as Umang Lais rather than the Buddhist pantheon. For example, Sanamahi is worshipped as Umanglai at Sugnu, Ahanthem and Wangoi.¹⁰⁴ They were given some autonomy within the fold of Umanglism and consequently evolved as a new religious factor in the post-Pamheiba Manipur. Now the problem is who brought the Buddhist elements into Manipur?

Before tracing the answer of this question, there is a need to stress one

basic point that the Meetei society is a conglomeration of aboriginal people, Brahmins, Pangals and other communities who migrated from the west and the east including, the Shan, the Burmese and the Chinese. The court library maintained the genealogy of the *Harams*, which can be defined as the immigrants from the west and east of Manipur who was absorbed into Meetei in the historical period.¹⁰⁵ Officially, they are two harams, viz., Nongpok haram (those hailing from the east) and Nongchup Haram (people hailing from the west of Manipur). Here it to present an instance of the assimilation of the Nongchup Haram (people hailing from the west of Manipur) who were almost Hindus, excluding the Pangals, into Meetei and the assimilation of their religious beliefs brought with them into Umanglaism, the state religion. There is an Umang lai named Laiyingthou Ramjee Ningthou venerated at Thinungai. Pundit Wahengbam Lukhoi, commenting on the deity, writes that a Hindu community [captives] from the west, who were the worshippers of Ram and Sita, migrated to Manipur and settled down at Thinungai. When they were assimilated into Meetei-fold by assigning them Yumnak (Meetei family title) and Sagai (Clan) their gods Ram and Sita were recognized by the Meetei king as Umanglais by giving them new names – Laiyingthou Ramjee Ningthou and Leibak Leima respectively. Similarly, goddess Kalika of Saktism was also worshiped as Khuleima at Takham and as Shija¹⁰⁶ Kalika, the consort of Umang god Khaplangba at Kakching.

The absorption of the *Nongpok Haram* (easterners) mostly the Shans, the Burmese and the Chinese, into the clans of Meetei is well recorded in the general genealogy, *Meibourol*, maintained by the court scholars. Around 63 yumnaks of Meeteis were from the eastern country (Burmese and Shans). The following is the list of few yumnak (family titles) and yek (clans) given to the easterners who were assimilated into Meetei.

Huiyam, Senjam, Chagam Mayum, Konsam, Usam, Khunbongmayum, Chingangbam, Sendangmayum, Nandeibam, Hikhambam, Chingsubam, Phuritsabam, Mungyommayum, Akhanbam, Khongbantabam, Senjam (Angom), Nandeibam (Angom), Usam (Angom), Senjam Laibak (Angom), Louriyam (Angom), Sangkhubam (Luwang), Yendrembam (Luwang), Achoibam(Luwang), Usam (Luwang), Khongbantabam (Luwang), Chaphalmayum, Ngaseppa, Hakham, Monphangmayum, Athokpam, Irom, Achoibam, sangkubam, Heikham, Ngasekpam, Samjetsabam, Heibithabam, Akhongbam, Charai mayum, Irungbam,etc¹⁰⁷

There was also a colony of the easterners known as Kabo Leikei in the north of the palace. In Cheitharol Kumbaba we find many instances of their

contributions into the administrative and military activities in ancient Manipur. Even the most powerful families of Manipur were enslaved Burmese nationals. For example, the Khombongmayum, the maternal family of Gambhir Singh was Kabo. The chronicle also recorded matrimonial and diplomatic relationships with the eastern Buddhist countries. For examples, in 1569 CE, Princess Sana Langmeirembi was married to the king of Kabo to become the queen of Kabo. Besides this, there are also many records of collecting war captives from the east. For example, King Khagemba collected many war captives, including sculptors and masons from the Buddhist kingdoms. The Chinese captives were located at Kameng.

Although their assimilations into the Meetei society were well recorded in the genealogy, the religious beliefs brought by them were not mentioned in the court documents as have been seen in the text Bamol Khunthoklon that the gods brought by the Hindu

Brahmins from the west, who came to settle down in Manipur, were clearly recorded. However, it can be presumed that as they came from the Buddhist kingdoms, as mentioned in the archaic Khongchomnupi Nongkaron that the Kabo people of the east worshiped their god *Phura* (Buddha), the Nongpok Harams must have been Buddhists. And it is possible that they brought with them their Buddhist pantheon and cults into Manipur, which were accordingly absorbed into Umanglaim. When they were absorbed into Umanglaim much of their originality seemed to have been lost.

Guru Nongsaba: A question

The god who was elevated to the position of supreme god during the reign of Khagemba was not Sanamahi but Nongsaba. During the reign of Khagemba (r. 1597-1652 CE) Nongsaba was recognized as an Umanglai by dedicating a five storied temple to him. According to *Nongsaba Laibui*, which is believed to have been written as late as during the reign of Charairomba (r. 1697-1709 CE) all the Umanglai gods, including Sanamahi, were described as the attendants of god Nongsaba. As it writes, “god Koubru served Nongsaba as his shawl, god Thangjing Koiren Ningthou as his back cushion, god Wangpuren, son of Wangnu Reima Khomchomphabi, as his carpet, God Marching , as his throne, god Nongpok Ningthou as his looking mirror, Telli Ningthou Sidaba as his clothes hanger, the sun god as his sekpin [canopy] and Pakhangba , as *arangchi*, goddess”¹⁰⁸

This shows the elevation of Nongsaba to the position of Supreme god and the other Umanglais as lesser gods. It was during the reign of Khagemba

that the Leithangbam family was assigned to manage the deity. The new school of *maibi*¹⁰⁹ known as Phura, which was established probably during the reign of King Khagemba, was also assigned to worship the deity. During the reign of Paikhomba, Princess Yaosombi was symbolically married to the deity Nongsaba and an elephant was also offered to the deity.¹¹⁰ All this shows that from the reign of Khagemba up to the accession of Charairomba the cult of Nongsaba is more popular than Sanamahi worship.

SANAMAHISM AS A SEPARATE SECT OF UMANGLAISM

Now the question is how Sanamahi was raised as the most popular god, and its worship grew up as a separate sect of Umanglaism. Surprisingly, the birth of Sanamahism is credited to Pamheiba (r. 1709-1748 CE) who is popularly known for destroying the idol of Sanamahi along with the idols of other Umanglais. Prior to the destruction of Sanamahi idol by Pamheiba, another similar act against Sanamahi is mentioned in the *Cheitharol Kumbaba* during the reign of Paikhomba (r.1666 -98 CE).

“On a Sunday, while there were not many people around, the royal great palace caught fire. Laiyingthou Taipang Khaiba[Sanamahi]’s royal palace also (in Kangla) was deliberately burnt down. Most of the wives (from the palace) were placed at each of the crossroads and the people also were very frightened.”¹¹¹

The detailed account of the event is unknown, but it indicates towards arson. The turning point of Sanamahi worship was the destruction of its metal idols during the reign of Pamheiba. Under the influence of Vaishnavism from the west, Pamheiba renounced the indigenous religion and adopted Ramanandi School. The chronology of the events which shows the destruction of the indigenous religion is given below:

Date	Events
31 August 1723	- The temples of Umang gods dismantled.
12 November 1723	- The Brahmins stated managing the temples of Nongsaba, Yimthei lai, Panthoibi and Taibangkhaiba (Sanamahi).
1 April 1725	- The King cremated the skeletons of his ancestors at the confluence of the Ningthee and Irrawaddy rivers. Hindu way of cremation adopted.
6 April 1725	- The King also adopted the title Maharaja.

- 5 June 1725 - Suttee introduced.
- 31 May 1726 - The idols of nine umanglais buried at Mongbahanba
- 22 July 1726 - The idols of Laiyingthou, Panthoibi, Laiwahaiba (Sanamahi), Lammapi, Soraren and Hutongpokpi destroyed.
- 28 July 1729 - Worship of Laiwahaiba[Sanamahi] started at Yumthei
- 12 June 1729 - The stone erected at the royal market was dragged to Mongbahanba for carving a statue of a Hindu god Hanuman.
- 2 November 1729 - The temple of Hanuman consecrated.
- 30 December 1729 - The temple and the image of Laiwahaiba [Sanamahi] consecrated. One Angom Chanu Leimakhubi Hanchapi (court lady) escorted to Laiwahaiba in marriage[symbolical].
- 4 January 1730 - King Pamheiba and his Guru Santadas immersed themselves in the river at Lilong. The Guru gave the Hindu sacred thread to the King.
- 20 June 1731 - A temple of Laiwahaiba (Sanamahi) constructed at Leishangkhong. A stone for the deity was also erected.
- 27 April 1732 - Another phura [brick temple] for Laiwahaiba (Sanamahi) constructed.
- 5 October 1732 - The Meetei books were destroyed. The image of Laiwahaiba also destroyed as unclean for the second time at Mongbahanba.
- 10 August 1733 - The image of Laiyingthou Phalloukhomba (Sanamahi), which was destroyed, was restored.
- 7 November 1737 - The King and 3000 persons [probably the head of every clan] took the sacred thread of Hindu.
- 17 August 1746 - The court officials offered wine to Sanamahi. [the term Sanamahi is first mentioned since this event]
- 11 September 1746 - The queen and the court ladies made a toast with wine before the image of Sanamahi at the market.

From the above chronology, it can be seen that among the Umang pantheon only Sanamahi was recognized and its idol recast by the King. The term Sanamahi is also first mentioned in the Cheitharol Kumbaba after the official recognition of the deity. Before that he was known as Phallou Khomba (*Phra-Along* Khomba) Shanti das didn't take part in the destruction of the idols. He was out of Manipur. When he returned to Manipur and knew that the idol of Sanamahi was destroyed; he advised the king that Sanamahi is not 'pagan' gods in the word of Sanamahi Laikan "*chaban chaba lai*". That means the god belonged to the most influential religion according to his view-point. He redefined the god as the avatar of Vishnu. This shows Shanta Das perhaps realizing the Buddha-Sanamahi relationship.

The Sanamahi Laikan gives an interesting account on this event. As he was renounced in Manipur, Sanamahi sojourned for three years in Kabo.¹¹² When Guru Santadas Gossai finally realized that Sanamahi and Vishnu are the same he asked King Pamheiba to recognize Sanamahi and worship along with Rama. He explained to the king that Sanamahi was the Avatar of Vishnu who speaks in person with the mortals. So, he asked the King to restore the image of Sanamahi. He also asked the king to take an oath that he would not give up worshipping Rama and Sanamahi by denouncing other Umanglais.¹¹³ From this evidence, it is clear that Sanamahi was given a special patronage by the royalties since the reign of Pamheiba, which led to the development of Sanamahism.

The destruction of the image of Sanamahi was not publicly conducted. It was done secretly in the night. If the temple was the property of the king, he might not do it secretly. That means the temple was controlled by somebody other than the king. It seems that the temple was controlled by a group of maibis who are autonomous to the government. The Sanamahi Laikan mentions a lady named Takhenbi as the priestess of Sanamahi. The domination of women in the politics and religion of Manipur will be discussed in the following sections.

PRE-HINDU MEETEI SOCIETY AND THE COMING OF BHAKTI MOVEMENT

Before delving further on this subject, there is a need to understand Pamheiba and his time. Pamheiba popularly known as Garibniwaz is now considered as a landmark of Hinduism in Manipur. He ruled Manipur for four decades from 1709 to 1748 CE. In the mind of the present generation, he is portrayed with his character as anti-traditionalism through plays and dramas

based on his life and the gossips about him prevailing among the masses. His act of burning *pyras* makes him a betrayer, although he was a political genius. One of his gossips is that Pamheiba was totally amazed when he saw a chemical magic (reaction of *sodium* with *water*) performed by Santa Das, and that he had accepted Santa Das's advice blindly and adopted Hinduism. But one never talks of his expert gun smiths who had experienced various ranges of chemicals. The Manipuri gunsmiths of Burma were well recorded in the later period.¹¹⁴ He was one of the leaders who attempted to consolidate mainland Southeast Asia into one nation.¹¹⁵ Sadly, the history of Pamheiba has been greatly abused and corrupted. His history is eclipsed by his myths. The renowned historian Gangumei Kabui condemns, "No other ruler in eastern India could boast of such a glorious military conquest in north east India and Burma in the early 18th century. Unfortunately, the myths and traditions have given a twisted picture of this great king. The myths and traditions were very powerful in a society where literacy and scholarship were the monopoly of the privileged few, and much importance was given to them by the colonial writers and following them, by the Indian historians.... The royal parentage of Garibniwaza or Pamheiba is well established by the chronicles, and all doubts created by the traditions of the eighteenth century are ill founded and false."¹¹⁶

In the early-nineteenth century Gambhir Singh and Nara Singh mobilized the Manipuris in Cachar to fight against the Burmese invaders by recalling the valour of their great-grandfather Pamheiba.¹¹⁷ His name was invoked as a symbol of nationalism. This shows that ill-rumors about him came in a much later period, perhaps during the reign of Churachand after the establishment of *Brahma Shava*. Most of the ill-rumours concerning him were concentrated in the 20th century rhetoric book entitled "*Senbi Mukaklei-Pamheiba Lalei Lathup*." The book claims that he was the illegitimate son of a Hindu palmist named Vishnu Goussami and Queen Nungthil Chaibi, wife of King Charairomba (r. 1697-1709 CE).

The Birth Myth of Pamheiba according to Lalei Lathup

This 20th century text is preserved at the Manipur State Archives. The author of this book is anonymous. It is possible that it was written in post-Bodhchandra period (r.1943-1952). The gist of the story in the book is as under:

Paikhomba was succeeded by Charairomba as king. One-day, Charairomba went to raid Chothe village as its chief refused to pay annual tribute. The chief of Chote was defeated. In that moment, Charairomba saw the beautiful daughter of the Chothe Chief. Her name was Nungthil Chaibi. The Chothe

Chief offered his daughter in marriage to Charairomba. Charairomba installed her as the Queen at Kangla Tongbi. As it was against the custom to install a war captive as queen, Nungthil Chaibi was kept aloof from the palace at Apong Hingol (within the Kangla fort). One day, a palmist named Shri Vishnu Gousammi arrived in the land of Meetei from the west. He secretly stayed in the residence of Nungthil Chaibi¹¹⁸. One night their child was conceived. The news reached the King, who shifted Nungthil Chaibi at Makeng Thangal village where Pamheiba was born. Years passed. One day Charairomba came to collect tribute at Thangal village. He was impressed by the personality of a young man, who happened to be the son of Nungthil Chaibi. He brought him along with two Thangal boys to the palace and established the Haomacha Loishang. Years passed. The Chief of Tusuk raised banner of rebellion. Charairomba raided the Tusuk. In his return journey to the palace, Charairomba was speared to death by Pamheiba, who became the king of Manipur. In his reign Pamheiba abolished all the Meetei traditions and introduced his father Vishnu Gopal's Hindu culture.

ANALYSIS

The above story is the explanation of how and why Manipur adopted Hinduism in the 18th century. The book *Lalei Lathup* was written two centuries after the death of Pamheiba. One defect of the author (s) of this book is his limited knowledge of the chronology and royal genealogy which makes the whole book a big imposter. Charairomba reigned for 11 years from 1697 to 1709. The book claims that all the above events occurred during the reign of Charairomba i.e. from his accession to the throne to his marriage with Nungthil Chaibi and from the birth of Pamheiba to his adulthood and from the marriage of Pamheiba to the murder of Charairomba.

The *Lalei Lathup* claims that Pamheiba was born after Charairomba became the king. But Pamheiba was born in 1690 and his mother Nungthil Chaibi had already died in 1696, before Charairomba became the king in 1697. The court chronicle *Cheitharol Kumbaba* records that Nungthil Chaibi gave birth to Pamheiba on 23rd December 1690 CE and that she gave birth to her second son Loiyumba on September 25, 1695. The second son of Nungthil Chaibi is almost unknown to the author(s) of *Lalei Lathup*. Her two sons were born before her husband Charairomba became the king. Six months after the birth of her second son, Nungthil Chaibi died on May 26, 1696. At that time, her husband Charairomba was not yet King. He was holding the post of *Yaiskul Lakpa*. All these events occurred during the reign of Paikhomba (r.1666-1697 CE). So, the question of Nungthil Chaibi's elevation to the position of

queen (*Meetei Reima*), as claim by the *Lalei Lathup*, is a fallacy. She is eulogized as *Meetei Reima* in the *Ningthourol Lambuba* and other literatures only after her son Pamheiba became the king as it was a royal tradition to address the mother of the reigning king as *Meetei-Reima*, even after her death, to reserve the matrilineal authority of the *Ningthou-Pokpi* (queen-mother). Here the archaic text *Chada Laibui* deserves a mention. The *Chada Laibui* is a royal chronicle of the queen mothers.

According to the royal chronicle *Cheitharol Kumpapa*, Pamheiba succeeded his father Charairomba in 1709 at the age of 20 years. The Chronicle also records the birth of Princess Shija Ahal, daughter of Pamheiba by his wife Haobam Chanu Tampak Shija, on November 12, 1706. His eldest son Shyam Sai was born to his another queen Arambam Chanu Tulshipriya on July 24, 1711. Supposing that Pamheiba was born during the reign of Charairomba (r.1697-1709), as claimed by the *Lalei Lathup*, then he might be not more than 7 years old when he became the father of Shija Ahal in 1706; not more than 10 years when he became the king in 1709 and not more than 12 years when he became the father of Shyam Sai in 1711, which are almost impossible. The book claims that Charairomba was murdered by Pamheiba in his return journey to the palace after the Tusuk expedition. According to the *Cheitharol Kumbaba*, the Tusuk expedition was conducted two months before the death of Charairomba. The chronicle records that Charairomba himself went to attack Tusuk on April 16, 1709 and returned after the victory over Tusuk on April 26, 1709. Charairomba died two months later on July 8, 1709. The Chronicle records the consecration of the temple of Laiwahaiba by Charairomba 18 days after his return after the Tusuk expedition. The 18th century book *Samjok Ngamba* records that Charairomba died of an illness. According to the oral traditions recorded in Brown's account, he died of a poisoned arrow of the Tusuk tribes. So, the story of his murder in the return journey after the Tusuk expedition is a mere fable. For all these reasons, one cannot simply consider *Lalai Lathup* as a historical account.

Like the Shakespeare's play *Merchant of Venice*, which was staged to propagate the hatred of the Jews in Europe, the *Lalei Lathup* is also a mere work of fiction, a sharp propaganda to defame the royalties and Brahmins who were the patrons of Bhakti movement in Manipur. In fact, there was no proper classification between fiction and history in Manipur until the publication of Dr. Lamabam Kamal Singh's novel *Madhabi* in 1930. Before it, all are treated as history. Even the myths of Arjun, Mahadeva and Vishnu were regarded as history in Manipur. There was no proper demarcation between myth and history. For instance, in the first page of his book "*Manipur Itibas*

(published in 1947) Mutum Julon Singh writes, "Manipur was first settled by Hindu god Mahadeva at Nilakuthi Giri (Nongmaiching hill)." Until recently, history was told in this way.

Birth Myth of Pamheiba in folksongs

There is also another version of the birth myth of Pamheiba told by *pena*¹¹⁹ performers which is clearly recorded by T.C Hodson in his book "The Meithei".

"The raja of Manipur, warned by prophecy that he would be slain by his son, has all boy babies in his harem killed at birth. But the mother of Garib Niwaz smuggles him away into a village where he is brought up by Naga tribesmen. Later, the raja has his suspicious aroused and orders all the children in that village to stand on a bridge and watch boats racing beneath; he had caused the bridge to be sawn through, so the children fell into the water and were drowned. But the guardians of Gharib Niwaz had been warned, so he escaped, grew up, entered his father the raja's service, accidentally killed him while they were hunting together, and then, the truth coming out, succeeded to the throne."

In his book "History of Burma" G.E. Harvey compares the above story with other similar myths found in other cultures. The myth is parallel with the story of the birth of Krishna contained in *Vishnu Purana*, the story of Herod and the story of Pandukabhaya of Ceylon.¹²⁰ The story of Pamheiba in the above two versions fit well to the popular prevailing hero myths found in most of the cultures. Benjamin Beit-Hallahmi writes, "The mythological hero is the son of royal parents, born in a different birth (often after a long period of childlessness), prophesied to be a danger to the safety of his father, who banished him (often by putting in a basket and setting it afloat). The child is then saved by poor people or animals, and only upon maturity does he discover his real parents. He eventually gains the love and recognition of his people achieves fame and greatness, and wreaks vengeance on his father, fulfilling the prophecy."¹²¹ Freud gives a possible origin of this plot as "family romance"¹²²

The history of Pamheiba is so mythically narrated that his abdication in favour of his second son [actually third; the second son Murari died in childhood] had been narrated in comparing with King Dasaratha of Ayodaya abdicating the throne in favour of his second son owing to the promise made to his second wife in time of their marriage. The *Garibniwaz Charita* (an 18th century account of Pamheiba) records that King Pamheiba took Gomti on a condition that her first born child would succeed him.

Pamheiba abdicated the throne in favour of his third son Chit Sai. The reason why Chit Sai was made king was that he was the eldest son of the reigning queen Gomti. It was a royal tradition that the eldest son of the reigning Queen should ascend to the throne. This tradition continued up to the 20th century. Queen Dhanamanjuri's adoption of a son born to her sister, who was also a wife of King Churchand, was probably to claim the throne for her adopted son through her position of the head queen.¹²³

Birth Myth of Pamheiba created by Colonial writers

The 19th century European writers refer Pamheiba to be a Naga descent of the Thangal village. Paikhomba died on January 9, 1698 CE. After a gap of around one and half month his nephew Charairomba ascended the throne on February 21, 1698 CE. This shows that after the death of Paikhomba there must be some political instability over the succession. Gangmumei Kabui writes, "During the last days of Paikhomba who adopted Charairongba to succeed him, there were a lot of intrigues in the court which might have compelled his mother [sic] and maternal grandfather to ensure the safety of the young prince by keeping him out of the palace in a distant village called Makeng Thangal inhabited by the friendly tribe in northern hills."¹²⁴ This event might lead to the creation of the gossip and rumour that Pamheiba was a Naga origin. The colonial writers who did not have any access to the royal chronicles might have collected this gossip in creating the birth history of Pamheiba.

FROM LEGEND TO HISTORY

Paikhomba, who ruled Manipur from 1666 to 1698 CE, had no surviving male issue. His successor Charairomba was his nephew. The royal genealogy is illustrated as under:-

Charairomba's father Tonsen Ngamba died on July 12, 1682.¹²⁵ At that time, Charairomba was only seven years old. Tonsen Ngamba was the younger brother of the reigning king Paikhomba. As he had no surviving male issue, Paikhomba adopted his nephew Charairomba as his own son. Paikhomba's son died of small pox in 1672.¹²⁶ Another reason of his adoption might be that Paikhomba shared the same mother with Tonsen Ngamba. Paikhomba had three-step mothers and six-step brothers. According to the royal tradition, Paikhomba also adopted a girl of the age of Charairomba. Her mother was a war captive who was brought in the palace from the territory of the Khumans. She belonged to the Sapam family of Uchiwa. When she was brought as a war captive in the palace, Nungthil Chaibi's mother was pregnant. In the palace, she gave birth to Nungthil Chaibi, who was adopted by Paikhomba as his own daughter. **It is supported by the chronicle as *Cheitharol Kumbaba* translated into English by Bamacharan under the order of Major Maxwell in 1891 records Pamheiba's mother Nungthil Chaibi as the daughter of Paikhomba.**¹²⁷ Nungthil Chaibi grew up with Charairomba in the palace. When she came of age Nungthil Chaibi had an affair with Charairomba. Their first child Pamheiba was conceived when Charairomba was 17 years old. As they are adopted sibling of the reigning king, their relation might be a social stigma.¹²⁸ Whether Nungthil Chaibi and her son Pamheiba were smuggled out of the palace in a distant village at Makeng Thangal remains a subject of further research. Four years before the birth of Pamheiba the relationship between the palace and the Thangal community was not in good term. It is evidenced from the fact that in 1686 Loinai Ngasingpa was sent at the head of a detachment of *Aballup* army to attack Thangal in which 20 Thangal rebels were taken prisoners. So, the claim that Nungthil Chaibi and her son Pamheiba taking refuge at the Thangal village is doubtful. The birth of Pamheiba in 1690 and the birth of another son of Nungthil Chaibi in 1695 were well recorded in the *Cheitharol Kumbaba* which suggests that they were born in the palace and their births were known to all. It is the nature of the *Cheitharol Kumababa* that every prince and princess born in the palace was recorded. Even the births of the influential kings like Bhagyachandra, Nara Singh and Churchand were not recorded in the *Cheitharol Kumbaba* simply because they were not born in the palace.¹²⁹ They didn't attempt to insert their birthdays in the *Cheitharol Kumababa* during the period of their reigns. The reason why this fact is mentioned is that in other versions of *Cheitharol Kumbaba*, the birth of Pamheiba is recorded as "King Mayamba¹³⁰ was born" and the death of his mother is recorded as "King Mayamba's queen mother

Nungthil Chaibi died.” This shows obvious manipulation of *Cheitharol Kumbaba* after Pamheiba became king in 1709. As Pamheiba was not born king, and her mother didn’t die as the queen-mother one may claim that these sentences were inserted later. Most of the surviving copies of *Cheitharol Kumaba* are second hand i.e. copy of one manuscript to another. While copying the manuscript the court pundits didn’t have any right to insert any extra sentence, but they always upgraded the title and designation of the princes and princesses while copying it. For example, Shija Naosem Ongbi [the princess who was married to Naosem family] was born; Ebungshija Wangkheirakpa [the prince who held the office of Wangkheirakpa] was born, etc. Titles and designation were very strictly considered. For example, one court scribbler was exiled for not putting *sbri* title in the name of the king during the reign of Nara Singh.

PUYA MEITHABA: A QUESTION

On October 5, 1732, Pamheiba collected all the *puyas* and burnt them all in front of the palace’s coronation building. On that day, the image of Laiwahaiba (now Sanamahi) was also destroyed at Mongbahanba. Today the event is commemorated as *Puya Mei Thaba* (burning of puyas). Etymologically the word *Puya* is a corrupt word of the Sanskrit term *Puran* or *Purana* which represents a collection of five distinguishing topics, viz. the creation of the universe, its destruction and renovation, the genealogy of gods and patriarchs, the reign of the Manus and the history of the Solar and Lunar races of kings. In Manipur also *puya* indicates the five subjects viz, Leisemlon (creation of earth), Nongsemton (creation of universe), Lairon (genealogy of gods and patriarchs), Ningthourol (account of the kings) and Meihourol (genealogy) which are altogether known as the five *lon*.¹³¹ It seems that puran is informally known as puya in Manipur. The chronicles and archaic texts find no trace of the word. Instead of *puya* the *Cheitharol Kumbaba* records the books on Meeteilgy as *Meetei Lairik*. Another term used was *korbek*. Now the following questions arose. Why Pamheiba did not burn the *Cheitharol Kumbaba*? Why didn’t he destroy the Cheinaron, the Numit Kappa and all the classics in his royal library? Why did he destroy only a bundle of selected books rather than the whole royal library? What are the contents of those books destroyed by Pamheiba? If his intention was to destroy all the books on Meeteilgy, he might be also burnt down the Cheitharol Kumbaba, the Ningthourol Lambuba, the Numit Kappa, the Cheinarol, and the hundreds of books on genealogy. Why didn’t he do so? And what are those selected books and their contents that were destroyed by Pamheiba? These simple questions make one doubt

the character of Pamheiba that was created. It is clear that Pamheiba didn't burn all the books in the royal library; only some selected titles were destroyed. On the contrary, many secular and religious books were written in *Meetei mayek* (meetei script) during his reign. Some of them were Samjok Ngamba, Takhel Ngamba, Charairomba Khunkum, Numit Kappa (enlarged volume) etc. This shows that his intention was not to exterminate the Meetei script or replace it with Bengali or Devnagari. Probing the subjects of the destroyed selected books is necessary to understand Pamheiba and his time. The list of the books destroyed by Pamheiba mentioned in the text *Miyat* is controversial since it was written two centuries after the event without any references.

The myth of burning Meetei scriptures

Many people are of the opinion that "*Puya meithaba*" is the burning of Meetei scriptures by Pamheiba. The so-called holy books or scriptures are the concept of Hinduism, Buddhism, Islam and Christianity. The concept of scripture doesn't exist in Umanglaism. In this religious system, its doctrines are not maintained in the form of book. It was not required, either. The doctrines have been surviving and thriving since antiquity up to the present day. Religious doctrines and teachings began to be preserved in the form of books or scriptures only when the religion had become endangered or extinct. Besides, the doctrine lost its originality only when it was written down. It became the monopoly of the upper classes (religious leaders, Brahmins, monks, kings and queens) who know how to manipulate it to their advantage. For instances, in the *Bhagavad-Gita* the Brahmins, the monopolist of Hindu society, became the highest class made by the God. The doctrine of Umanglaism is orally preserved in the form of songs, rituals and dances by the three institutions of *maibi*, namely, Sanglen, Langmai and Phura. For instance, *Hijan Hirao*, which deals on the harmony between human and forest, was not preserved in form of book or scriptures. Instead, the *maibi* preaches it in the form of ritual songs in the Laiharaoba.

As there were no such scriptures of the religion of Manipur, the burning of them by Pamheiba in 1732 is a myth! Now the question is what are those books destroyed by Pamheiba as recorded in the court chronicle?

Pamheiba and his environment

Before probing the answer of the above question, one need to first study and appreciate the social milieu in which Pamheiba was compelled to burn those selected books. Manipur was not submerged by Hinduism overnight. It

didn't come suddenly like a tsunami. The process continued for a long period and for generations and Pamheiba was a grain of sand on the seashore which was carried away by the tide of this movement. It can be compared with Hijam Irabot's initiation into communist politics when Marxist doctrines began to spread in Bengal and Southeast Asia. In the mid-twentieth century, Irabot adopted communism because it was an easily accessible doctrine to fight for the cause of his nation. Bhakti movement also entered into Northeast India in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries, same as the communist movement spread throughout this region in the early twentieth century; but the bhakti movement took root in this region and gave birth to two great reformist saints, Sankaradeva in Assam and Bhagyachandra in Manipur.

One can take and analyse the example of how Churachand (1891-1951) adopted Vaisnavism for his cause. The influence of Hinduism in the court of Manipur was reduced dramatically after the death of Gambhir Singh in 1829 as observed by the British officers who were posted in Manipur in that period. It means that Vaisnavism was declining. An example of it was that the boy king Chandra Kirti started learning English, although the court Brahmins called it as the language of *Mallecha* (untouchable). Finally even the children of the Brahmins and girls were sent at the English school run by George Gordon, the British Political Agent. The influence of Hinduism increased suddenly again during the reign of Churachand not because he had become philosophical or impressed by the doctrine of Vaisnavism, but for an economic cause. The king had to raise easy money to be paid to the British government as tribute and to meet the expenses of luxurious European lifestyle of his family. Bhakti was a tax gathering mechanism in his time. Feudal taxation such as the *mangba-sengba* rituals, tax for a Vaisnava marks (*chandam senkhai*), etc were imposed on the people. Charairomba and Pamheiba also adopted Bhakti movement as a measure for their own causes which may be political, social or economic. Before one goes further to the problems of Pamheiba one need to first study how the Bhakti movement became an easily accessible 'doctrine' for a cause in Manipur.

Exodus of Hindus to the mainland Southeast Asia

Naturally, people are dynamic. They migrated from one place to another for better life. In the ancient history of the mainland Southeast Asia, one has seen how the Tais completely transformed this region when they were driven out from their home land Nanchao by the Tartars in the 12th century. The establishment of Tai kingdoms in the mainland Southeast Asia was the outcome of it. Recently, the Indo-Pak war in 1971 led to the migration of a

huge number of Bangladeshi refugees to Burma, Tripura, Assam and Manipur which totally changed its politics within a few years. These are the two examples of human migration; one from the beginning of history and another from the present day. Between this two time gaps, the instances of human migration into this region and the changes brought by them would be in thousands. Immigration of Brahmins from the Gangetic valley to the mainland Southeast Asia is an example among the thousands. Hinduism was brought with them in this region. As Brahmins brought Hinduism into Manipur, the British brought Christianity as early as in 1814; the Buddhists brought Buddhism into Manipur.

The Brahmins played a major role in the politics of south Asia. When they shifted in the Southeast Asian, they claimed the same power. It is evidenced from the accounts of how lavishly they lived in the courts of Ahom, Tripura, Cachar, Manipur, Burma and Thailand. Hinduism entered into Southeast Asian countries in different forms.

The demand of Hindu doctrines in the mainland Southeast Asian kingdoms can be seen in most of the events. Statecraft of these kingdoms was based on Mahabharat, Ramayana, Bhagavat Gita, Arthasastra, etc. Tripura waged war against Manipur for a copy of Bhagavat Gita, which was lent by King Charairomba of Manipur and refused to return it back. The statecraft of post Pamheiba Manipur was based on *Charairomba Khongum* which was an edited Manipuri version of Panchatantra written by Vishnu Sharma in between 100 BCE to 500 BCE.

How the two great Indian epics had influenced the Southeast Asian nations to a great extent can be seen in the naming of the capitals and the composing of royal genealogies. The capital of Meetei kings began to be styled as Manipur of Mahabharata; the capital of Thailand as Ayodhya of Ramayana; the capitals of Burma as Amarapura and Ratnapura; the Cachar as Hiramba Desh. The kings of Thailand began to claim as the descendents of Rama of Ramayana; the kings of Burma as the descendents of Judisthira, the eldest Pandaba of Mahabharata; the kings of Cachar became the descendents of Bhima, the second Pandaba; and the Meetei kings as the descendents of Arjuna, the third Pandaba. As mentioned above there was not a single royal court of the Southeast and Far East Asian kingdoms and empires, which was not influenced by Buddhism or Hinduism. Lokendra Arambam writes, "The divine right of the kings of Southeast Asia to rule over the realms of people and populations were accentuated with rites and rituals emanating from the cultural sources of Sanskrit and Indic philosophy."¹³²

In the early nineteenth century, the Manipuri Brahmins and the Brahmins

from central provinces of India migrated to Southeast Asia with intense hatred of the British. It is the Brahmins who called the British as *Mallecha* (untouchable). In the early nineteenth century the Manipuri Brahmins who lived in the court of Burma persuaded the Burmese Emperor to declare war against the British.¹³³ Fifty years before this there is no reason that they would not do the same thing against the Great Mughuls. For instance, Santa Das complained to Pamheiba against the Muslim nawabs for ill-treating him.¹³⁴ It was one of their motives. But the motive of the kings of Southeast Asian countries was a different story.

Choosing the Hindu school

Charairomba was the first Meetei king who adopted Hinduism. He fasted and took the name of Hindu on April 9, 1704.¹³⁵ The 18th century text *Samsok Ngamba* records his Hindu name as Petambar Singh. For the first time the *Cheitharol Kumbaba* records building of the temples of Hindu gods Kalika and Krishna in 1707. According to the 18th century text *Sanamahi Laikan* the sect adopted by Charairomba was Sakta. It is possible that Pamheiba also adopted Hinduism with his father Charairomba. The *Sanamahi Laikan* records the initiation of Pamheiba into various sects of Hinduism. He adopted the following sects under the given corresponding gurus.

No.	Sect of Hinduism	Guru	Year
1	Sakta	Brahman Banmali	1704
2	Sakhya	Gangadhar	Post 1709
3	Goudiya(Cheityana School)	Shri Gopal Das	
4	Ramanadi School	Santa Das	to 1738

Sakta sect of Hinduism is the worship of mother goddess like Kalika, Durga and other female energy. Before he adopted Bhakti as his doctrine, Pamheiba was a believer of Sakta cult. During the reign of Charairomba the image of Goddess Panthoibi was installed. The name of the kingdom as Mekheli (the European spelled as Meckley) is derived from Sakta interpretation. In the Tantras and Puranas there are four principal sites (mahapitha) they are Jalanshara, Ossiyaana, Purnagiri and Kampura. At these places the Goddess' tongue, nipples and vulva (yoni) are said to have fallen. The most important of these seats as a living place of pilgrimage is Kamrupa

where Sati's yoni fell.¹³⁶ It is believed that the place where the waist of the Goddess fell is named Mekhili.

The records from the *Cheitharol Kumbaba* summarized the enterprise of Pamheiba.

7 Lamta 1656 SE (1 March 1735 CE): Those who followed the *Ramanti* were fined.¹³⁷

2 Inga 1658 SE (11 June 1736 CE): All those who were followers of *Ramanti* were fined.¹³⁸

5 Yinga 1661 SE (11 June 1739 CE): Ningthem (King) and others took *pramartha dharma*.¹³⁹

5 Yingen 1661 SE (11 July 1739 CE): Prince Yibungo Tangka Sai and other took *lukun* (sacred thread). Those who refused to take *lukun* in the past also took *lukun*.¹⁴⁰

20 Yinga 1667 SE (19 June 1745 CE): the building of the temple of Krishna started at Kiyang Ingkhol.¹⁴¹

10 Kalen 1670 SE (5 June 1748 CE): Maharaja Garibniwaz [Pamheiba] abdicated the throne in favour of his son Yipungo Chit Sai. The royal father lived with Moirang Thawa the Maharani in Ramsala. All those who were following the Gouriya way of life were fined.¹⁴²

The above chronology suggests that Pamheiba renounce Ramanadi School and adopted Pramatha Dharma. It is not clear whether Pramatha Dharma is the Cheityana School or other religious sect. But the construction of the temple of Krishna and the punishments given to the followers of Gaudiya School after his abdication shows that in the end of his reign, Pamheiba popularized Gaudiya or Cheityana School in place of Ramanandi School.

BHAKTI MOVEMENT

Bhakti is a South Asian devotional movement emphasizing the love of a devotee for his or her personal god. Bhakti characteristically developed around Vishnu's incarnation as Rama and Krishna. Practices include reciting the god's name, singing hymns, wearing his emblem, and making pilgrimages.¹⁴³

In response to the social milieu and needs of Bhakti

For Pamheiba, Bhakti was an easily accessible doctrine to fight for his cause. Initiation into new thought means compromising some of the old thought. For example, when a kingdom became a republic the kingdom has to compromise its old institution of the royal family. The influence of Tantric Buddhism has already been discussed in above sections. The religion coming

from the east and the west brought a system called Tantrism in Manipur, which came to affect Manipur to a great extent. Tantrism is not a religion. It is a culture. Tantrism found in Manipur was brought by Buddhism, Saktism and Savaism. According to Moirangthem Kirti, the social history of present day northeast India from the year 1200 to 1700 is dominated by Tantrism.¹⁴⁴ It would be worth mentioning here the social condition of Assam, which compelled Sankaradeva to spread his bhakti movement in the sixteenth century:

“Most of the people of Sankaradeva’s time were Siva and Sakti worshippers, and their religion was known as Saktism.... Both the chief scriptures of Assam Saktism, the Kalika-Purana and the Yogini-Tantra, belong to the left-handed school of Saktism, and enjoin blood sacrifices and various esoteric rituals. The ritual consisted of 5 Ms. viz, *madya* (wine), *mamsa* (meat), *matsya* (fish), *mudra* (ritual position of fingers) and *maithuna* (sexual union). These forms were a permanent feature during the time of Sankaradeva. Blood sacrifice was sacred to Kamakhya Devi... Magic and witchcraft played a major role in Assam. This went to such heinous extent of a child being cut off the body of a pregnant woman who had completed her full term of months. There were many other similar abuses prevalent in Assam, the cause of which was blind faith in magic...tantrism with its religion of blood and sacrifice, as well as magic with its heinous practices held sway in Assam... the majority of the Hindus in Assam were under the spell of the Saiva and Sakti cults with their tantric practices. They were not following tantrism as a philosophy, but gave more importance to its outward way of life based on sex and food, and rites such as bloody sacrifices to gods and goddesses.”¹⁴⁵

In Manipur also one finds many references to animal and human sacrifices associated with religion before the coming of Bhakti movement. Here is an extract from the Cheitharol Kumbaba:

“The year of Santham Mayang, Sakabda 1540 (1618 CE)... (they) performed an appeasement rite to the sovereign god Marching. (They) sacrificed wild boars, dogs, ducks, fowls, pigeons, and many other living creatures. They performed appeasement rites at every watering place...”¹⁴⁶

“...The year of Nongpokpam Khompa 1608 Kum Sak... In the month Yinga (May/June 1686 CE), Yirom Loinai Ngasingpa and others attacked Thangal. They captured 10 persons in battle... The prisoners were killed at Moirangkhom in the festival of Laihou... The year of Thounaocham Koirang 1611 Kum Sak... Thursday the 11 of Sachiphu (31 March 1689 CE) they erected Ukrong in which 12 prisoners, including Khoiphurang from Maphou, Keiyangle from Wokprum and Champirung from Loitai, were killed... The

year of Chanampa Sara 1619 Kum Sak... Sunday the 23rd of Sachiphu (14 April 1697 CE) they went to fell a tree to make Ukrong... Monday, the new moon day (6 May, 1697 CE) they erected the Ukrong for Queen Sicha Ponglen Khompi, in which 17 persons were sacrificed.”¹⁴⁷

There were also negative effects of Tantrism. *Potsem* is an example. It is an evil craft secretly practiced to harm other people. Still today Meetei practice wearing *yantra* on their arms, neck and waist for many purposes, especially to ward off evils and bring good fortunes. This *yantra* is an amulet consisting of a mantra along with the sketch of the coiled snake. Mystic diagrams are called *yantra*.¹⁴⁸ The word “Oja”¹⁴⁹ used today to address our teachers is a corrupt word of *Ojbâ* meaning ‘expert practitioner of Tantra’ or ‘exorcist, folk healer’¹⁵⁰. According to Major McCulloch, the princes used the term *Ipu* to address the elders. The term Oja was first mentioned in the 18th century book entitled *Arong Nandakumar Laibu Ningba*, a Buddhist jataka story, as a compound word *Oja-Guru*.¹⁵¹ Tantrism had entered into the core of the Umanglaism that a new school of *Maibi* (religious specialist) began to emerge under the name “Phura”. The maibis of this school use bell as their medium to invoke the god and meditation. In the Vrajayana Buddhism, bell is used as a medium for meditation.

In the beginning of the reign of Pamheiba, before he adopted Ramanadi school of Vaishnavism, the *Chietharol Kumbaba* gives a reference of a punishment inflicted to the practitioners of *Potsem* when it became a threat to the king and queen. The chronicle records:-

“The year of Thoutam Khongchom 1632 Kum Sak.... Friday, the 1st of Yingen (27 June 1710 CE) seven persons including Yirom Loinai Ngasingpa were fined for practicing *potsem* against the queen.... The year of Asangpam Haochau 1637 Kum Sak ...Sunday, the 28th of Hiyangkei (24th November 1715CE) Prince Kongyampa, younger brother of the king, and Sanlam Apang, these two, were practicing *potsem* against Ningthem (king)..... Sanlam Apang was hanged to south of the graveyard... Prince Kongyamba and his wife Sanlam maiden were also executed at the royal graveyard.”

The term “*potsem*” is first recorded in the chronicle during the reign of Pamheiba and also the punishment given to those who practiced it. This shows that *potsem* was already in practice in Manipur and it became illegal since the accession of Pamheiba to the throne in 1709. Recording in the court chronicle means it has become a national issue. According to Moirangthem Kirti Singh, the evil practices of Tantrism such as *potsem* (tantric craft similar to sorcery), *Laisanaba* (black magic), *kapsinnaba* (fight using Tantric crafts) and so on were

practiced by the Manipuris.¹⁵² The king took certain steps to prevent the society from such cultures. The penalty introduced by Pamheiba against the practice of Tantrism was followed by his successors. Here are a few examples from Cheitharol Kumbaba:

“... 1701 Kum Sak (1779 CE)... Sunday, the 26 Yinga (8 August 1779 CE), Soraisampa from Kharam Lanta was arrested with his wife and children on the charge of practicing potsem.....1709 Kum Sak (1787 CE)... 5 Kalen (22 April 1787 CE)... One Thinguwa Niranchan was exiled to Sekmai for practicing potsem... Friday, 24 Langpan (5 October 1787 CE)... one maipa Hanglai was exiled to Suknu for practicing potsem... The year of Thanga Hera 1728 Kum Sak and 1081 Chandrabda.... Sunday the 22nd Kalen (10th May 1806), Naorem Murari was exiled to Suknu for practicing *potsem*.....Wednesday, the 22nd of second Thawan (3rd September 1806 CE) Ayekpa Lapa and Thokchao Murari were exiled to Phoukakchao for practicing *Potsem*....”

In Manipur, *potsem* is alive. Still today the villages which are beyond the influence of strict Bhagyachandra School are noted for such craft of Tantrism. The *Loi* villages like Phayeng, Leimaram, Andro and Khurukhul deserves mention. The Meetei inhabited villages like Thanga, Kwakta and Kakching are well known for learning Tantric crafts. A list of titles which were believed to be destroyed by Pamheiba might be the books on Tantric occultism, magic, spell, etc¹⁵³ According to the 20th century text *Miyat*, 122 books were collected and burnt in front of Uttra. Among them the books Taoroinai Yangbi, Pakhangba Yangbi, Pakhangba Naoyom and Sanamahi Naoyom are mentioned prominently. It is also not reasonable that all the existing religious books and objects of worship were destroyed for the purpose of the extermination of the social evils associated with Tantrism because Pamheiba also introduced suttee (widow burning) after his conversion to Vaishnavism. It would not be wrong to assume that Pamheiba was continuing the process of enhancing and consolidating the feudal ideology by following the *Bhaki* doctrines and strengthening the patriarchal authority which has been developing since the reign of Khagemba (r.1597-1652 CE).¹⁵⁴ “In the great revolt against all old religions when patriarchal sects enforced their preeminence, most Tantric scriptures were burned [in India].”¹⁵⁵ The Hindu patriarchal sects burnt the tantric scriptures, which exalted female power, and the tantric temples were either destroyed or converted into Hindu temples. The followers of Tantrism were expelled from north India and they took refuge in Bengal, Assam, Tibet and Nepal where they established their own power centers. Kamakhya was

one of their most important centers. There was a period in the history of northeast India when the society was under the spell of occult rituals of Tantrism and Saktism, including human sacrifices at temples. The Vaishnava Bhakti movement started by Sankaradeva in the sixteenth century in Assam was a movement against such tantric practices and sacrifices associated with Sakti worship and Buddhism.

The underlying motives of Pamheiba can also be examined through his administrative reforms along with the religious conversion. He reorganized every department of administration and made a number of improvements in the existing pattern. In 1715, he entrusted the administration of justice to his noblemen.

On January 6, 1747, there was a discussion that the service rendered compulsorily to the king by the four *panas* should be abolished. This shows decentralization of power to the noblemen. In 1727, he imposed *lanlup* on his hill subjects. In 1729, he divided his subjects into four *panas*- Khapam, Naharup, Ahanrup, and Laipham- for administrative convenience. The division of the population into *pana* indicates the elevation of the enslaved people into state subjects. His religious conversion reflects his enterprise to secure loyalty of his subjects in the means and relations of productions – military services, corvee labour - through the doctrine of *Bhakti* (complete surrender to the higher authority).

Suttee – humiliating the feminine power (Matriarch)

Suttee is an example of women degrading as sub-ordinate to man in the Hindu society. In the pre-historic period women attendants and slaves were buried alive on the funeral of their master as evidenced from the archaeological findings in China and Mesopotamia. In Europe women are burnt alive as heretic by the Roman Catholic to suppress women's domination in the religion. These are the few markers of the transformation of the society from matriarchal to the patriarchal system.

There was no such evidence in the history of Manipur until the adoption of Hinduism in the eighteenth century. The court chronicle records the first evidence of such nature as follows:

“The year of Langmaithem Loicha 1647 Kum Sak, Thursday, the 25th of Yinga (June 25, 1725 CE), Prince Sanahal Murari died. He was cremated at Maglen, the royal cremation site. His two *manainupi* (female slaves) were burned alive on the funeral pyre.”¹⁵⁶

The term *manainupi*, which literally means female-slave, was begun to be used as honorific address for a wife in the Hindu period. It continued to be

used by the age-old royalties still today. But in the above example, the term *manainupi* indicates female- slaves rather than the wives of Prince Murari since he died young at the age of eight. So, it is not the practice of suttee but an imitation of it. After this event, there are three events of the practice of suttee recorded in the court chronicle.

“The year of Loukurakpam Moirangpa 1657 Kum Sak...Thursday, the 7th of Sachiphu (31st March 1735 CE), Pamon Lakon died. He was cremated together with his two widows. Thursday, the 6th of Kalen (28th April 1735 CE) Wayenpamcha the Nongthonpa died. He was cremated together with his two widows....The year of Kshetri Goverdhon 1659 Kum Sak...Saturday, the 28th of Wakching (18th January 1738 CE), Tampaknai Keirungpa Thongaipa died. He was cremated together with his two widows... The year of Moirang Koireng 1662 Kum Sak...Thursday, the 26th of Thawan (18th August 1740 CE) Nganglom the Hitakphu Phanpa Hanchapa died. He was cremated together with his widow Hanchapi.”

Addressing the wives as slave and burning of widows on the funeral pyre of their husbands show the attempt to degrade the position of the women. The replacement of women *maibis* by the Brahmins in the management of the royal temples on November 12, 1723 CE also shows the usurping of the religious authority from the priestess by the king himself. The attempt of Pamheiba was to transform Manipur from a female dominating society into a male dominating society on the model of the Hindu society. It was an attempt to transform the Meetei society into a strict patriarchy by demeaning the supreme status of women. This was already felt in the pre-Charairomba period.

The Meetei society in the pre-Charairomba period

The records in the *Cheitharol Kumbaba* up to Mungyamba (r.1562-1597) are very limited. A period of 50-years reign of a king is completed in a few sentences. The period from Pakhangba (r.33 CE) to Mungyamba (r.1562-1597) is covered in only 28 leaves of 12 lines each. The chronicle began to record the day, month and year of an event since 1666 CE only.

Among the limited pages, we find the records of the births of the queens and princesses. But in the post- Pamheiba period when the chronicle began to record even the death of royal horse there is not a single record of the birth of queen. In the strict patriarchal monarchy, the powers of queens are limited. But how the births of the queens were recorded in the pre-Charairomba period? This puts in doubt whether matrilineal monarchy existed in the pre-Charairomba period.

There are many evidences of the existence of a society in the pre-Charairomba period where women and their powers were highly valued. The chronicles are full of accounts of this kind. There was also the evidence of the matrilineal authority in the government. We have been seeing Manipur from the top of Kutu Minar and London Bridge. But the view of Manipur from the top of the Koubru Mountain will have a different experience. It is completely different from what we have been interpreting from the Indian or European context. The history of Manipur is full of anomalies

“ Sakabda 1365 (1443 CE) while Meetingu Ningthoukhomba was away attacking Akla, and when Meetei Reima (Queen) Linthoi Ngambi and others along with the whole land settled temporarily at Tangkham, all the Tangkhuns from the mountain range revolted and marched down to attack and take all the people (of the plain) as prisoners. They failed and they were all captured and detained.¹⁵⁷The year of Haoroibam Muba 1576 Kum Sak..... Meetei Reima (Queen) Takenbi and Khurai Reima (Queen of Angom) Sanakhonbi left to attack Kuyong. They were victorious over Kuyong. In this expedition they captured four women and one man, altogether five prisoners. They were victorious over Khutlai and captured Ponglenpa in battle.”¹⁵⁸

The court ladies led the royal army in the war. It was not exceptional as in the case of Jhanshi Rani in India and Joan of Arc in Europe. But it was recorded in the chronicles as a normal routine of the palace ladies of Manipur. Efforts have been made to interpret Queen Linthoi Ngambi, who defeated the chief of Tangkhul riding tribesmen, Queen Sicha Phongda Lokpi (Kuranganayani), who killed Raghav Moran, as extraordinary court ladies but in the true sense, they were not extraordinary. Today they are quoted comparing with Jhanshi Rani and Joan of Arc because our outlook has changed. Jhanshi Rani was extraordinary in the Indian society where women were treated as slaves to their husband. In Europe, where women were burned alive as heretic, Joan of Arc is admired “as a sane and shrewd country girl of extraordinary strength of mind and hardihood of body”¹⁵⁹. But women’s going to war was normal in Manipur society. The maximum events recorded in the court chronicle *Cheitharol Kumbaba* of the pre-Charairomba period were full of women domination in politics as well as in military exercises. The records of the *Cheitharol Kumbaba* in the pre-Charairomba period are completely different from the records of the post-Pamheiba period. The chronicle recorded the birth of princess and queens and their activities as the birth of princes and their activities was recorded in the pre-Charairomba period. Here is an extract from the *Cheitharol Kumbaba*.

“Sakabda 1445 (1523 CE)... Meetei Reima (Queen) Serembi was born....Sakabda 1468 (1546) Yipemma Sanahal was born.... Sakabda 1470 (1548 CE).... Khuraileima Khuroi Ngampi was born...Sakabda 1477 (1555 CE)... Chongpombi was born....Sakabda 1478(1556 CE)... Meetingu Mungyangpa’s mother Lamphen Ngampi died... Sakabda 1486 (1564 CE) ... Meetingu Mungyampa and Meetei Reima Serempi dedicated the erection of a wooden pillar in memory of Meedingu Chalamba... Sakabda 1487 (1565 CE) Meetei Reima Serembi’s mother, the Satpam Maiden, died.... 1488 (1566 CE)... Khurai Leima Kapombi died....Sakabda 1490(1568 CE)... Yipemma Nungthil Chaipi was born... Yipemma Chirang Chaipi also was born.... Sakabda 1491 (1569 CE) Meetei reima Serempi dedicated a tree.... Sakabda 1495 (1573 CE)... Yipemma Koirempi was born... Sak 1496 (1574 CE) Sna Hekpi, the Kapo Leima, left....Sakabda 1500 (1578 CE)...Yipemma Thingkrachaipi was born... Yipemma Koirempi was born... Sakabda 1502 (1580 CE)... Meetei Reima (Queen) Mongkhom Ngambi was born....Sakabda 1503 (1581 CE). Yipemma Thingkara Chaipi died of smallpox... (1506 CE)Khuraileima Takhen Chaipi was born... Sakabda 1507 (1585 CE)... Mayang Leima Koirempi left (for Mayang).. Sakabda 1509 (1587CE)...Yipemma Changpomp’s mother, Heirok Ngampi, died... Sakabda 1510(1588 CE) Yipemma Takhel Chaipi was married... Sakabda 1511 (1589 CE)... Yipemma Mayangnu was born... Sakabda 1512 (1590 CE)... Yipemma Koirempi was married... Sakabda 1513 (1591 CE)... Yipemma Tosennu was born... Sakabda 1514 (1592)...Khurai Reima Kharoingambi dedicated a tree... Sakabda 1515 (1593CE)...Yipemma Sarembi died....”

But in the post-Pamheiba period the activities of women in politics were declining. Even the births of influential princess were not recorded. So we can simply consider the reigns of Paikhomba, Charairomba and Pamheiba as the transition period of a women dominating society into a male dominating society. Cheitharol Kumbaba was edited during the reign of Bhagyachandra. The copies of the chronicle which have been surviving till today are second hand copies of this edited volume. Whether the original was lost during the Burmese invasions, or it was edited on the model of patriarchy remains a question which needs further research. The list of the kings from Pakhangba to Charairomba which claim to belong to a same patriarchal line deserves to be reviewed. Pamheiba after he adopted Hinduism ordered his court scholars to compose the genealogy of the country. The *Cheitharol Kumbaba* records:-

“The year of Thingpaicham Karu, Sakabda 1660... Friday, the 10th of Yingen (June 27, 1738 CE), they began to write the genealogy of the seven *salais*.”¹⁶⁰

All the old thought and practices cannot be wiped off completely in a century or millennium. Even today we are using stone grinder, which is a continuing practice since the new Stone Age. There must be remnants of the past Manipuri society dominated by female. Manipur has been full of matriarchal tradition to this day. Still today the market of Manipur is a monopoly of women. The religion of Manipur was also controlled by women. Even the male maibi had to dress like women maibi. Until the abolition of monarchy in the 20th century, there were certain royal women offices where the male employees had to be addressed as *ebemma* which is like addressing madam to a man. There was also the women's court run only by the women. There was also a body of elderly court women who controlled the moral of the king. They even had the power to punish the king for a certain crime. These are the remnants of the past. The matriarchal tradition is fossilized in the ritual of Saroi Khangba in which elderly women of the community came out with sword in their hand and perform the ritual to protect the community from evil spirits.¹⁶¹ The fashion of blackening the teeth, which continued up to the twentieth century by the Manipuri elderly women, is also another remnant of this tradition.¹⁶² The Meetei especially the royal clan was originally matriarchal is also evidenced by the heavy bride price retained until the late 20th century. It is known as *mangkhat*. Here is an example from the Cheitharol Kumbaba:

“In the year of Thoukraicham Longkhum, Sakabda 1592 (1670 CE)...In the month of Kalen (April/May), a cattle-drawn palanquin and other items arrived (as a bride price) for the meetei maiden to be married to the Mayang king. The mother of the maiden regarded the price as too little and sent them back. An elephant and other items were sent as the (bride price)”¹⁶³

The extended families of the royal clan still continued the practice of bride price or bride wealth with some variation as *Kwagok hanba*.

Adopting mother's family titles

Ura Konthouba's daughter was married to the king of Moirang. Their descendants took the surname of their mother Ura until the third generation.

In the *Cheitharol Kumbaba*, the second marriage of the Queen- Mother of Nongyingphaba is recorded in this sentence, “*Nongyinphabaki mamapu Angoupanpa kyampana Ongeiye.*”¹⁶⁴ This sentence shows that Angom Chief Kyamba was married to the Queen-Mother of Meetei rather than Queen-mother married to the Angom Chief. After that Angom Chief began to wear the red dyed egret's feather, the insignia of the Meetei royalty, as his head gear. This shows the Angom chief's claim of Meetei royalty by marriage.

Man living in the parental house of his wife is called *yawong inba* in Manipuri. Saroj Nalini Arambam Parrat interprets *yawong inba* as “a custom among the Meeteis where the groom lives in the parental home of the bride. The stay could be of a permanent nature or temporary. Except in cases where the wife is the only child of her parents the groom is often looked down upon. This may be a trace of a matriarchal custom.”¹⁶⁵ The *Ningthourol Lambuba* records that Naothingkhong stayed at his first wife Pitanga place at Selloi Langmai. The *Naothingkhong Phambal Kaba* also records his living at the parental house of his second wife and third wife before he became the king of Meetei. Before he became the king in 1709, Pamheiba also stayed in the parental house of his wife Haobam Chanu. The chronicle records, “On November 12, 1706 Ningthem Mayampa (Pamheiba)’s eldest daughter Sicha Aahan was born while he was living in the *Tampak*.” The term *Tampak* is either used as the parental house of a prince’s wife or the residence of the Crown-prince.” The wife of the Crown-prince is also addressed as *Tampak Leima*. The *Cheitharol Kumbaba* records King Nara Singh staying at his wife’s parental house.

There are many evidences of the Manipuri royalties staying permanently in the parental houses of their wives and mothers. Sometime, the princes took their mother’s parental house title as their non-official surname. For instance, in the genealogical book Sangai Phamang many princes were addressed with their mother’s surnames. King Devendra’s sons were recorded as Thangjam Sana and Chongtham Sana. Three of the King Nara Singh’s sons were recorded as Haobam Sanatomba, Laishram Sana and Chingakham Sanatomba. The titles Chongtham, Laishram, Haobam, and Thangjam were the parental family titles of their mothers. These princes settled in their mother’s parental houses. This tradition continued up to the twentieth century. Rajkumar Sanajaoba, son of Prince Sanatomba and grandson of King Devendra, was recorded as Loitam Sanajaoba in the government records. The title *Loitam* was his mother’s surname. He was one of the six royalties arrested in connection with the 1904 incident. These are perhaps the remnants of the matrilineal system.

The family structure of the royal clan of Manipur was matrifocal than strict patriarchy. It was a tradition that a royal husband often came to live in his wife’s parental house.¹⁶⁶ Their children were officially reckoned through the father’s line and non-officially through the mother’s line. Suppose that a male royalty marries with a female who belongs to the Chingakham family, then their children would officially reckon as a royal descent or ningthemcha and non-officially reckon as the mother’s line i.e. “Chingakham Sana” meaning

“royalty of Chingakham family”. In a case when a royal husband takes more than one wives from different families their children would unofficially reckon their respective mothers’ family title.

In the case when the royal clan followed polygamy the following structure will follow:

Father		Mother	Children title	
			Official	Non-official
Ningthemcha or Rajkumar or Royal descent.	Maries	1) Wife belongs to	Rajkumar/	Laishram
		2) Laishram family.	Rajkumari	Sana
		3) Wife belongs to	Or	
		Maisnam family	Ningthemcha	Maisnam
		4) Wife belongs to	/Shija	Sana
5) Wife belongs to		Angom Sana		
		Khunbongmayu		Khunbongma
		m family.		yum Sana

Development of the Meetei monarchy saw a gradual transition from matriarchy to hereditary patriarchy. The *Chada Leibui* is a royal chronicle which recorded through the line of the queen mother. The chronicle Ningthourol Lambuba was started recording with the invocation to Queen mother Leinung Yaibirok, mother of Pakhangba, and it was written chronologically from the queen mother to king pattern. The celebrated court chronicle *Cheitharol Kumbaba* is not organized under the heading of a particular king or in pure patriarchal line as we have seen in the edited printed copies. It is written continuously without the heading of any patriarchal monarch.

THE QUEEN MOTHER AND GODDESS YUMJAO LEIMA

Here it is worth mentioning the royal tradition associated with Goddess Yumjao Leima and the Queen mother. Yumjao or Yimjao denotes royal house and Leima, queen or chief. The Ningthouja clan (royal clan) has around 100 extended families, the largest of all the seven clans of Meetei, because the war captives and immigrants were usually assimilated into the Ningthouja clan by assigning Ningthouja yumnak (family titles of Ningthouja). Among the extended families of the Ningthouja clan the royal blood or the descendents of the kings or queens were distinctly identified as “Yumjao Naota”. Yumjao means royal house and naota means offspring. To support this argument some examples from the Cheitharol Kumbaba are given below:

“1715 Kum Sak ...Sunday the 25 Langban (29 September 1793 CE) the

Langpoklakpam family [Ningthouja clan] applied to Meedingu Chingthangkhomba to acknowledge them as yumjao naota by claiming that they were descended from Yipungo Ahan... Meedingu Chingthangkhomba summoned almost all the members of the royal family and knew that Yipungo Ahan did not have any issue and that the Langpoklakpam family was descended from King Thangpi Lanthapa [who ruled Manipur in 1302 CE]. The Langpoklakpam family was exiled to Moirang along with women and children for giving false evidence.¹⁶⁷

Fifty one years later the Langpoklakpam family was acknowledged as Yumjao naota (royal decents) by King Nara Singh in 1844 as the Chronicle records, "Thursday the 12 Hiyangkei 1766 Kum Sak (21 November 1844 CE) as it was said that the Langpoklakpams were the the descendents of Prince Sanahal Khongchompa, son of Yiputhou Khagemba, Shri Maharaja recognised them as Yumjao naota."¹⁶⁸

The above examples show that King Chingthangkhomba did not acknowledge the Langpoklakpam as *yumjao naota* although they were proved to be the descendents of King Thangbi Lanthaba. Whether they were exiled for giving false evidence, although they were proved as royal blood or there were certain rules to be acknowledged as Yumjao naota deserves further research since Nara Singh's acknowledgment of them as *yumjao naota* was not because they were descended from King Thangbi Lanthaba, but they were proved to be the scions of Prince Ahan Khongjomba, son of Khagemba. *Yumjao* can be defined as the royal household; *Naota*, as off- spring and Yumjao Leima, as the Leima or chief of this household and the guidance of the king. She also controlled the life and death of the king. It is traditionally believed that she appears as mortal being on the death of the king. All the powerful queen-mothers were integrated into Yumjao Leima after their death. Yumjao Lairenbi herself was the all time reigning queen-mother.¹⁶⁹ All these show that the most powerful ruling entity was always the Queen Mother, who was represented by the deity Yumjao Leima. In the ancient period, the heads hunted in the war were offered to this goddess. The Meetei kings ruled the country in the name of the queen mother. They waged war in the name of their queen-mother. Here is an instance from the Cheitharol Kumbaba,

"Sakabda 1629 (1707 CE)... 5 Sunday Hiyangei, they went to raid Nungkhan in the name of the king's royal mother."¹⁷⁰

Vestige of matrilineal authority in post Charairomba period

The abdication of Pamheiba in favour of his third son Menkhomba was

eulogized by the court scholars comparing with King Dasaratha abdicating the throne in favour of his second son Bharata of the Hindu epic Ramayana. It is possible that the third son Menkhompa also known as Chit Sai and Khaki Lanthapa succeeded his father on the ground that he was the eldest son of the reigning queen. His mother Queen-Meetei Reima Gomti Paikhu Lanthapi ascended the throne for the second time on 15th December 1738 CE. The list of the Head Queens and their reigning period as recorded in *Cheitharon Kumpapa* are shown below:

- (a) Haopam Chanu Keithen Thanpi – 28th August 1709 CE to d. 8th April 1716 CE.
- (b) Haopam Chanu Mayampi – 27th May 1716 CE to 21st August 1717 CE.
- (c) Ngangpam Chanu Panga Keithen Thanpi- 21st August 1717 to 9th September 1725 CE.
- (d) Wayenpam Chanu Gomti Paikhu Lanthapa – 17th September 1725 CE to 28th May 1738 CE.
- (e) Moiranthem Chanu Premganga Maklang Khompi – 2nd June 1738 CE to 3rd November 1738 CE.
- (f) Wayenpam Gomti Paikhu Lanthapi – 15th December 1738 CE to?

After the abdication of the throne, Pamheiba was driven out from the capital by his consort Gomti, who was the reigning queen. This shows usurping the authority of kingship by Queen Gomti in the name of her eldest son Menkhomba.

Another example of the queen mother's dominating the power is found in the history of Manipur after the death of Gambhir Singh. The dowager Queen-Mother Kumudini's claim to the highest position of the country on her husband, Gambhir Singh, death is notable. She was the second consort of King Gambhir Singh. She attempted to usurp the regency from Nara Singh by attempting on his life. She also encouraged and funded the princes in Cachar to revolt against Nara Singh.

There is also another unpopular historical event, which remains as an oral tradition amongst the royalties in Manipur. In 1850, Nara Singh died. He was succeeded by his younger brother Devendra. The sons of Nara Singh led by Bubon Sana and Angou Sana fled to Cachar. They secretly smuggled Chandra Kirti, who was kept under house-arrest in Cachar, into Manipur and usurped the throne. Chandrakirti was made king, Budon Sana, heir apparent and Angou Sana, the third in line to the throne. On the same night Bubon Sana and Angou Sana were not permitted to enter their residences by their mothers,

the dowager-queens of Nara Singh, for the reason that they drove out their uncle from Manipur and installed their third cousin Chandrakirti on the throne. Their mothers encouraged Bubon Sana and Angou Sana to revolt against Chandradrikiti. They revolted against Chandrakirti but they were defeated and fled to Cachar. This event also shows that the revolt was the design of the dowager- queens of Nara Singh who attempted to rule Manipur as queen-mothers. Another similar story was the design of Dowager- Queen Chingakhm Chanu Devahuti. In 1804 Chourjit revolted against the reigning king Madhuchandra, who sent his brother Marjit to quell the revolt at Maklang. A battle ensued. In that moment Chourjit's mother queen Chingakhm Chanu came to the battle field and cajoled Marjit to join with Chourjit against Madhuchandra. Marjit's mother died when Marjit was young. He was adopted by Chourjit's mother. Marjit took the advice of his foster mother and joined with Chourjit and usurped the throne from Madhuchandra. Chingakhm Chanu Devahuti became the Queen Mother.

The clash between these two systems is clearly seen in the early 19th century text Gambhir Singh Nongaba which was composed by the court scholars Dayaram Louremba and Nabashyam Ningthoujamba in 1830s under the direction of Regent Nara Singh (r. 1834-1844 CE). In this book women were leveled unfit to rule a country. The question of women's ruling a country would not be quoted in this book if there was no question for Queen-Mother Kumudini's claiming to the highest position of government in the country after the death of her husband Gambhir Singh. The government records also supported this argument. When Chandrakirti secured his position on the throne, his queen mother Kumudini returned to Manipur. This event was recorded in Cheitharol Kumbaba on a more even lavish scale. Kumudini also installed her daughter Shija Tamphasana as the yuvaraj or heir- apparent to the throne which aptly summed up the argument. In fact, during the reign of Chandrakirti the government of Manipur was dominated by Kumudini and her parental house Maisnam. Even the nobles were not allowed to pass the matrilineal house (Maisnam) of Chandrakirti on the palanquin.

Other example is that the spectators who came to witness the execution of Crown prince Tikendrajit and General Thangal were all women. The following is the examples of women uprisings in Manipur.

- 1) The women uprising against King Chandrakirti's order for elephant hunting expedition before the harvest month.
- 2) The woman's uprising against the *lallup* imposed by the British in 1904.
- 3) The second woman's uprising against the export of rice from Manipur.

- 4) The woman's uprising against the water tax.
- 5) The *Meira paibi* movement of the late 20th century.

BHAKTI MOVEMENT AND FEUDALISM

The term feudalism has been commonly used to describe the socio-economic system in the medieval society of European. According to R.S Sharma, feudalism cannot "be regarded as the monopoly of Western Europe" and that there cannot have "a clear cut formula about feudalism". He argues "Feudalism appears in a predominantly agrarian economy which is marked by a class of landlords and one of subject peasantry." In the Meetei context, feudalism is roughly defined as *loucha nai*- the system that prevails between landlords and tenant paddy farmers or serfs. Meetei state emerged as a result of taking over other tribes and enslaving their population and absorbing of manpower from the east and west. The court chronicle records many events such as collection of skilled-manpower like Burmese masons and Shan artisans from the Chindwin river basins and resettling them in Manipur by giving them Manipuri family professional titles (*yumnak*). For instance, the forefathers of the *Konsam* (means bronze-smith) family were the artisans collected by the Meetei from Kabo. They were naturalised by giving them family titles.

The absorption of the *nongpok haram* (easterners) mostly the Shans, the Burmese and the Chinese and *nongchup haram* (westerner) mostly *mayangs* into the clans of Meetei is well recorded in the general genealogy, *Meihourol*. The *pangal* populations and the Bisnupriyas of Ningthoukhong are the descendents of the war captives taken by King Khagemba from the west. The war captives were compelled to labour in their respective trades encouraged to marry local wives and became naturalized subjects. For instance, the Court Chronicle *Cheitharol Kumbaba* records:-

"Laiyingthou Khakempa was victorious over the Mayangs. They captured thirty elephants , 1,000 guns, and a colony of 1,000 *pangans*, including swordsmiths, brass smiths and other skilled men, makers of trumpets and long drums, those who could make brackets, washer-men, horse grooms, and grooms for elephants, all these were captured. All those *Pangans* who were captured alive were allowed to establish an institution.

"Friday, 27th Langpan 1727 Kum Sak (20 September 1805 CE): a village was established at Kakching for the captives from Mayang (Cachar) numbering 107 persons."

" Sunday, the 27th Yingen 1728 Kum Sak (13 July 1806 CE), Parakusum Hachari persuaded the Mayangs, who were collected by Meeteingu Wairang

Pamheiba and given land for settlement, that they should not accept to take wife because if the king gave them wife they could not return to their native land. Parakusum Hachari was exiled to Wangoo.”¹⁷¹

Captain Gordon gives a vivid account of how the war captives or slaves were naturized as state’s free subjects or Meetei.

“...some who were Mussulmans in Bengal are here recognised as Rajputs [Meeteis]. The process of purification in this case is rather curious: the candidate for re-admission to caste being obliged as a preliminary step to live and eat with Nagas for twelve months. Even Kabas [Kabos] and Nagas find little difficulty in becoming Rajputs [Meeteis], although Hindu of inferior caste seldom or never do so. I have seen several Kabas [Kabos] who have taken up their residence in Manipur since the cession of their country to the Burmese, sporting the Rajput string and tilak; and the late Raja [Gambhir Singh], whose mother was a Kaba [Kabo], acted as guru to one or two even while residing in their own country, and thus converted them into Rajputs [Meeteis]. Naga slaves soon assume the family names of their masters and their caste too, and on acquiring their freedom, which many do, set up as regular Rajputs; indeed a considerable proportion of the population, and several of the first families in the country, are well known to be so descended.”¹⁷²

Around half of the Meetei population rose from enslavement of the westerners from Cachar and easterners from the Chinwin river basin. Under the feudal society, the enslaved people were elevated to the position of serfs. Manipur entered into the stage of feudalism when the accumulated manpower through slaving and war captive were organised under the *pana* system which recognized them as state’s free subjects (but politically not free), but under this system they were compelled to work as serfs through *lallup* system (Corvee labour). One can infer that naturalization of war-captives or bondage people led to the emergence of serfdom in Manipur. The entire Meetei population was divided into six *panas* and *lois*. Of the six *panas* four were of the high class or the earlier ones viz., *Nabarup*, *Aballup*, *Khabam* and *Laipham*, and the remaining two, *Hidakphu Phamba* and *Potsbangbam*, were the inferior ones or the newcomers. These *lups* were the manpower for military and economic activities. James C. Scott writes, “The resources of manpower at the core were not only crucial for food production; they were military essential to the defense and expansion of the state against its rivals.”¹⁷³

Lallup is a corvée-style labour. Corvée, under the feudal system is compulsory, unpaid labor demanded by a lord or king and the system of such

labor in general. *Lallup* refers to 10 days' manual labour to the state for all able bodied men ranging from 17 to 60 years of age. *Lallup* is a form of taxation paid in labour or in the form of personal service. It is the main administrative practice found in feudal Manipur. Until the British occupation of Manipur in 1891 almost all the state's public works were built using *Lallup* labour.

Here is it sufficient to quote the account of Captain George Gordon, who served as the British political agent in Manipur from 1835 to 1844, to illustrate the socio-economic organization in Manipur:

“The government (of Manipur) appears to be framed after the true Chinese paternal model: the idea is that of a large family; the *raja* is the head or father, the royal connections the members, the chiefs the stewards, and the people are the servants. The latter are, indeed, divided into several classes, but all are designed in some way or other to minister to the wants or state of the royal family. Some provide grain, others salt, other cloth, other silk, other grass, other earthen pots, &c, &c. Every one has his duty, and every duty has its agent; each class has its sirdars, who after deducting their own allowances and the shares for other men in power, hand over the remainder to the head steward, who, in case it be not already cash, sells the surplus for his own and master's benefit. All these classes, however, are termed tributaries, are deemed inferior, rarely given personal attendance, and if they go on military expeditions generally act as porters.

The next great division of the people five attendance the *sepoys*, then the horsemen, spearmen, messengers, house-builders, doctors, barbers, and in short, every description of people needed for the police or for the defense of the country. The *raja* had the power of degrading any one to a disreputable rank, or of elevating to a higher; and when we further remember that no man here can resign in disgust, but most continue through life to be in some way or other a servant of government, we perceive the power of *raja*, for good or evil, is usually great. The whole people look up to their government not only as the source of honor and emolument, but also as the authority on which all in every grade depend for the rank they hold in society, and to which they look as their model of manners, fanfarons, and religious observances.”¹⁷⁴

The above account is an example of **a society which was vertically organized through reciprocal patron-client relationships. The clients pay their produce to their patron in return they were protected by their patron.** In order to develop this mutual relationship between patron and client (showing loyalty to the king or lords) the Meetei kings or the ruling class turned their attention in developing and pursuing the idealist doctrines

which could enhance such patron-client system. *Umanglaim* could not give the basis need in feudal ideology. Attempts were made as early as during the reign of Khagemba (r.1597-1652 CE) by developing the concept of Atiha Guru Sidaba and later elevating Lai Nongsaba to the position of Supreme God¹⁷⁵, but to no avail. The introduction of the term “*Lainingthou*” (Godly King) and prostration also supports the enterprise of Khagemba. The Chronicle records, “In the year of Thongbam Mangsa 1530 Kum sak... They also started addressing Meetingu Khakempa as *laiyingthou* (Godly king) since then. Prostration also introduced. Precious gifts were given to those who came to prostrate.”

Since the 17th century, the main philosophy embraced by the Meetei kings to implement their project for this transformation is bhakti, which was the best religion to organise feudal society. This marks the transition period from slave-holding society to feudalism.

Why Bhakti movement? “Bhakti was the basis need in feudal ideology”, writes D.D Kosambi, “.. Bhakti, [means] personal devotion: To whoever composed that document, bhakti was the justification, the one way of deriving all views from a single divine source. The essence of fully developed feudalism is the chain of personal loyalty which binds retainer to chief, tenant to lord, and baron to king or emperor. Not loyalty in the abstract but with a secure foundation in the means and relations of production: land ownership, military service, tax collection and the conversion of local produce into commodities through the magnates. The further development of feudalism ‘from below’ meant a class of people at the village level who had special right over the land (whether of cultivation, occupation, or hereditary ownership) and performed special armed service as well as in tax-collection. To hold this type of society and its state together, the best religion is one which emphasizes the role of bhakti, personal faith, even though the object of devotion may have clearly visible flaws.”¹⁷⁶

“The need of security was the prime cause behind the evolution and growth of the Bhakti movement. The need was too of socio-economic type. In the early medieval literature it is stated that there is only one mean/source of security i.e. Bhakti. By practicing Bhakti one could have favour of almighty power or his master.

“So this very need of security, for seeking the protection from the powerful, some ethical and moral norms were prescribed known as Bhaktibhava. They were derived from different social rules and regulations. Since the Bhakti was a seeking of security so we find several means i.e. many types of Bhaktibhava (earlier form of five types of Bhakti) it is interesting to note that these

types of relation seeking the protection were similar to different kinds of loyalties and devotion expressed by subordinates towards their lords, masters, saviours or protectors. For instance the above types of loyalties and devotion of slaves for their masters, of feudal chiefs for their paramount lord, of peasants for land lords and of wage earners and lower peasantry for their peasant Lord, of son for father were also found prevalent during the early medieval period in India.”¹⁷⁷

Romila Thapar also writes, “... the more widespread lack of these [peasant uprisings in India] is partly attributed to the ideology of bhakti directing attention away from the impoverishment of material condition.”¹⁷⁸

Here it is also worth reproducing an extract from the *Chinese Repository*¹⁷⁹ regarding the foundation of the idol of Govindajee in Manipur by Bhagyachandra to support the view that *Bhakti* means seeking protection from powerful, the essence of feudalism.

“About the year 1780, an image of Govinda was publicly consecrated with much ceremony in Manipur, by the grandfather [Bhagyachandra] of the present *Raja* [Ningthem Pisak]. This was the first national profession of that faith, though its votaries had previously been resident there. At the same time a proclamation was issued by the *raja* stating that, in order to avert the recurrence of such calamities as then oppressed them (the invasion of the Burmese) he wholly made over his country to his celestial proprietor, henceforward holding the government in his name.”

Bhakti movement arrived in Manipur with Nimandi, Ramandi and Gaudiya schools of Vaisnavism. Nimandi was propagated by Charairongba and Ramanadi by his son Pamheiba (Garibniwaz).

The failure of Nimandi and Ramanadi in Manipur led to synthesis of indigenous Umanglaim and Gaudiya School during the reign of Bhagyachandra (r. 1763-1799 CE) which led to the foundation of Bhagyachandra School. In short, Bhagyachandra School is the adaptation of Vaisnavism to Manipur. Besides, it would not be wrong to say that Bhagyachandra School, like the Sanamahism, is also a branch of Umanglaim. It became Manipur's national religio-philosophy until the reign of Bodhchandra (r.1941 to 1955). The abolition of *lallup* system in 1891 may be considered as the first political step towards the end of the feudalism in Manipur, but many relics of feudalism still continued to exist along with the Bhagyachandra School, and its influence remains on the institutions established during the reign of Churachand (r.1891-1942), for instance, the *pothang* system, the Brahma Sabha, the *Chandon Senkhai* system, etc.

CONCLUSION

From the above discussion, it is clear that the Meeteis were familiar with the concept of syncretism. Umanglaim developed from a village level pagan form of religion to a national religion which served as a mechanism for the consolidation of various enslaved and indigenous communities towards the making of the integrated and homogeneous Meetei nation-state. During the critical stages in the process of state-building, Umanglaim witnessed two major reforms, which enhanced the idealistic doctrines of the ruling class. Its synthesis with some elements of the Mahayana Buddhism led to the development of new branch called Sanamahism since the reign of Khagemba (r.1597-1652 CE), and its synthesis with the Bhakti movement led to the development of another branch called Bhagyachadra School since the reign of Chingthangkhomba(r. 1763-1798 CE). Umanglaim has played important role as an instrument of policy in building the Meetei nation. Umanglaim has survived and thrived up to the present day by virtue of its syncretism, amalgamation, absorption, dynamic translation and its action of synthesis.

Endnotes

- 1 Kanglei Umanglai Haraoba (Imphal,1988)
- 2 Umanglai Haraobagi Thouram (Imphal, 1986)
- 3 R.K Achoubisana “Lai haraoba” in *Dance of Manipur: the Classical tradition*, ed., by Saryu Doshi, Mumbai: Marg 1989
- 4 Wahengbam Lukhoi, *Lai Haraoba*, (Imphal: L. Asok Kumar, 1989)
- 5 Lai means deity. So, umang lai can be interpreted as the gods of Umangism.
- 6 O. Bhogeshwar Singh, *Sanamahi Laikan*,(Imphal: 1972), p. 49
- 7 Ibid. also see *The Court Chronicle of the Kings of Manipur: the Cheitharon Kumpapa*, ed. Saroj Nalini Arambam Parratt, (New York, Routledge), pp. 72-73, “ Khumukcham Langmeigi Kum Sak 1543 ... there was a strong wind and one *uleisang* orchid which was in the *Umang* of Muwa Ningthou (umanglai) was blown off.”, pp. 72-73
- 8 Khulem Chandrasekhar Singh, ed. *Loiyumba Shinyen* (Imphal: Moirangthem Ibotombi Singh, 1975)
- 9 Nats: human beings who met unnatural deaths like drowned in river, cyclone etc.
- 10 L. Ibungohal Singh and N. Khelchandra, eds. *Cheitharol Kumbaba*(Imphal:1989), p. 41
- 11 Ningombam Ibobi Singh, *Hindu Pravadin*, (Imphal, 1981), pp. 182-183.
- 12 O. Bhogeshwar Singh, ed. *Moirang Ningthoiron Lambuba* , p. 48-49
- 13 The four cardinal Umanglais are Koubru, Nongpok Ningthou, Thangjing and Wangpuren.
- 14 Op.cit. Wahengbam Lukhoi, p.13
- 15 Koireng is a corrupt word of Koren or Koiren
- 16 Oinam Bhogeshwar, *Moirang Ningthourol Lambuba*, p.90-91
- 17 Thounaojam chanu Ibemhal, *Haoreima Sambubi*(Imphal,2000), p.189
- 18 Chanam Hemchandra Khaba, ed, *Konthoujam Lairenbi* (Imphal,1985)
- 19 Op.cit. Wahengbam Lukhoi, p. 166
- 20 “Five Pakhangba: 1) Leinung Nongja Pakhangba, 2) Thangja Lila Pakhangba, 3) SendrengPakhangba, 4) Nonta Lairen Pakhangba, 5) Chote Thangmei Pakhangba; Four Pakhangba (Pandit Achaoba): 1) Lolang Pakhangba 2) Sendreng Pakhangba, 3) Thangja Lila Pakhangba 4) Nongdren Pakhangba”, *Notes on Meithei (Manipur) Beliefs and Customs*, by J.C.. Higgins, ed. M.John Parratt , Manipur State Archives , India., 1998., p. 160
- 21 L.Kunjewori Devi, *Archaeology in Manipur* (New Delhi, 2007), p.89
- 22 Oinam Bhogeshwar Singh, *Toreirol Lanbuba* (Manipur State Akadami, Imphal, 1984), p.115
- 23 Op.cit., Wahengbam Lukhoi, pp.177-184
- 24 Tara Devi is considered as female Bodhasattava in Mahayana Buddhism.
- 25 M. Kirti Singh, *Manipuri Samaj Hougatlakpa amasung Chaokhatlakpa* (Imphal: L. Mukta Singh), p. 96.
- 26 John Crawford, *Journal of an Embassy from the Governor-General of India to the Court of Ava in the Year 1827*, London: Henry Colburn, 1829, *Appendix*.
- 27 Father Adriano Di St.Thecla, *Opusculum de Sectis apud Sinenses et Tunkinenses* (A Small treaties on the Sects among the Chinese and Tonkinese), (Cornell Southeast Asia Program Publications: NY, 2002), p. 183
- 28 Quoted by Godfrey Higgins in his book “Anacalypsis, an Attempt to Draw Aside the Veil of the Saitic Isis; or the An Inquiry into the Origin of Languages, Nations, and Religion, Vol. I,

- (London: Longman, 1836), p. 153
- 29 A.K.Sharma, Manipur, The Glorious Past (Aryan Books International, New Delhi, 1994), p. 25.
- 30 Gangmumei Kabui, History of Manipur, Vol.I, Pre-colonial Period (National Publishing House, New Delhi, 1991) p. 44
- 31 J.C. Higgins, Notes on Meithei (Manipur) Beliefs and Customs, ed. John Parratt, Manipur State Archives, 1998, p.106
- 32 L. Kunjeswari, Archaeology in Manipur (New Delhi:2007), p. 164
- 33 Amaibi: Manipurida Samanism (Imphal: Arambam Yoimayai, 2006)
- 34 Moirangthem Chandra Singh, ed. Khongjomnupi Nongkaron, p. 6
- 35 S. Sasananda, History of Buddhism in Assam (300 BC- c.1300 AD) (Bahri Publication, New Delhi)
- 36 Romila Thapar, Early History, *From the Origins to AD 1300*, Penguin Books, 2002, p. 482
- 37 Leithak Leikharol, ed. Bhagya Singh Yenkhoiba, (Imphal:1988), p.12
- 38 Memchoubi, Amaibi: Manipurida Samanism (Imphal: Arambam Yoimayai, 2006), p. 87
- 39 Sylwia Gil, The Role of Monkhood in Contemporary Myanmar Society, for Friedrich Ebert Stiftung, September 2008, p. 2
- 40 Swapna Bhattacharya, "The Ari Cult of Myanmar", Uta Gartner and Jens Lorenz, eds. Traditional and Modernity in Myanmar, pp.251-252
- 41 Quoted by Chanam Hemchandra, Numit kappa, p. 3
- 42 For example, *sun chatpa*, *Sun drang* etc are used as slang in Manipur meaning the lack of reality.
- 43 Memchoubi, op.cit., p.89
- 44 David Leeming, A Dictionary of Asian Mythology, (Oxford: New York 2001) pp 114-115, "Mandala is Sanskrit for 'circle', and is used in various ways by peoples in many parts of the world- especially Asia – as a representation of sacred wholeness or significance. The snake biting its own tail (Ouroboros) can be a *mandala*. Tibetan Buddhists and North American relatives of central Asian cultures- for example, the Navajo Indians- use mandalas in sand paintings, as part of curing or initiatory ceremonies. The *mandala* in such cases is a representation of creation itself, and appropriate setting for the recreation of the person who is ill or not yet initiated into the 'real' world of knowledge. In the same sense a mandala can be a kind of labyrinth through which the initiate or prigrim must pass in order to achieve union with the 'center'. Vedic altars of various geometrical designs were arranged so that the various deities could have appropriate seats for rituals. Square mandalas are used in Buddhist and Hindu tantric traditions... For the Buddhist, the mandala can be a potent symbol of liberation, which various gods surrounding the sacred center of Enlightenment. In esoteric Japanese Buddhism (see Shingon sect, Japanese Buddhism), the Womb Whole *Mandala* and the Diamond World *Mandala* are central symbols of the process of Enlightenment- elaborate designs containing deities surrounding the central figure of the cosmic Vairocana, a Buddha much revered by the Shingon sect."
- 45 See Donald K. Swearer, Becoming The Buddha, (Princeton University: New Jersey, 1934), p. 63-66
- 46 A similar myth is also found in the Siva Purana as a competition between the two sons of Shiva, Skenda and Ganesh, to see who could circumambulate the earth first.
- 47 Steven Collins, Nirvana and other Buddhist Felicities, University of Cambridge, first published 1998, p. 583

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- 48 Tara (Buddhism)-Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia. [http://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tara_\(Buddhism\)](http://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tara_(Buddhism)) (accessed 20/1/2014, 2.19 pm)
- 49 3.6 Prajnaparamita and other Buddhist deities | Rijksmuseum Volkenkunde. <http://volkenkunde.nl/nl.node/1049> (accessed 20/1/2014, 3 pm)
- 50 R. K. Jhalajit, *A Short History of Manipur* (Imphal, 1992, 2nd edition) p. 95
- 51 Saroj Nalini Arambam Parratt op.cit, pp. 64-82
- 52 Ibid., p.36
- 53 Wahengbam Lukhoi Singh, *Lai Haraoba* (Manipur State Kala Akademy, Imphal, 1989, First edition) p. 177-189
- 54 Oinam Bhogeshwar Singh, ed., *Sanamahi Laikan*, p. 20
- 55 *The Court Chronicle of the Kings of Manipur: the Cheitharon Kumpapa*, ed. Saroj Nalini Arambam Parratt, (New York, Routledge), p. 97
- 56 Ibid., p.110
- 57 Ibid.,p.141
- 58 Ibid., p.162
- 59 *Sanamahi Laikan*, op. cit., p.32.
- 60 Memchoubi, op.cit., p.84
- 61 *Interpretation in Religion*, eds. Shilomo Biderman and Ben-Ami Scharfstien, (E.J. Brill: 1992) p. 159
- 62 Paul R. Fleischman, *An Ancient Path*, (Vipassana Research Publications, WA: 2008) p.171
- 63 Arthur Braverman, *Mud and Water: the Collected Teachings of Zen Master Bassui* (Revised and expanded Edition: wisdom Publications, USA, 2002),p.108
- 64 *Father Sangermano, A Description of the Burmese Empire*, (Susil Gupta, London, First edition, Rome 1833, fifth edition 1966) p.60
- 65 Thanuram Gogoi, *Friendship between India and Thailand*, 1981, ch.1, p.1. Quoted by M. Narimattam in "The Valley In Blossom"(Spectrum Publications: Delhi) p. 48
- 66 Ch. Manihar.
- 67 *Sanamahi Laikan*, op. cit., p.31.
- 68 Bernard Faure, *The Red Thread: Buddhist Approaches to Sexuality* (New Jersey: Princeton University Press, 1998), p. 50, "During the sexual union, the male practitioner is supposed to meditate 'in the forehead or in the sex organ.' This meditation is called samapatti, a term that in Mahayana means the achievement of a state of equanimity in which all mental constructs are gradually eliminated, but that in Vajrayana refers more specifically to the union of Hevajra and his female companion Nairatmya. During the preliminary ritual "invocation" of the deity, it is a meditation through which the practitioner sees himself as male (Tib. Yab) united to a goddess (Tib. yum), or as a female (yum) united to a god (yab). In the course of the ritual, this mental copulation can be translated into a real coitus with a "wisdom woman" (vidya), or "seal" (mudra). During the act, the practitioner must concentrate on his bodhicitta, a term that in Mahayana refers to a psychic and mental state, the "thought of awakening," but that is used here in a more specific sense, to designate the semen. The thought of awakening (bodhicitta) is identified with the bindu, the "drop", that is, the product of the fusion of the seed (sukla, the "white," semem = upaya) with the ovum (rakta, the "red", the menses = prajna). The bindu is the egg, the germ, just as the thought of awakening is the germ of a new being. This practice is related to the "coitus reservatus" with a female partner (mudra). The

trick is to stir this seminal essence without losing it through ejaculation, so that it may ascend through the central artery into the seat of Great Bliss located in the brain. The process, which is said to lead ultimately to the union of Bliss and Emptiness, can be practiced either alone during meditation, or with a female partner. Likewise, the term "Great Bliss" (mahasukla) means not only a spiritual state but also 'sexual fluid.'"

- 69 John Powers, Introduction to Tibetan Buddhism, (Snow Lion Publications: NY, 1995) p. 28
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